

ANNOTATION GUIDELINE FOR FREE-TEXT ACTIVITY FUNCTIONING INFORMATION: SELF-CARE & DOMESTIC LIFE

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	4
1.1	Use of this Guideline	4
1.2	Introduction to the ICF and conceptualization of function.....	5
1.3	Conceptualizing Self-Care & Domestic Life	7
2	ANNOTATION DATA.....	8
3	ANNOTATION TOOL	9
4	ANNOTATION SCHEMA.....	9
4.1	Entities and Mentions	11
4.2	Attributes and Values.....	14
5	GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS	19
5.1	Annotate for semantics and not syntax	19
5.2	Grammatical and Typographical Errors.....	19
5.3	General Guidelines for Annotating Mentions	19
5.4	General Guidelines for Attributes and Values	21
6	SCDL-SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS	22
6.1	SCDL Sub-entity Mentions.....	22
6.2	Action Sub-Mentions.....	26
6.3	Assistance Sub-Mention.....	42
6.4	Quantification Sub-Mention	46
6.5	Score Definition Mention	48
6.6	Instructions/Questions Mention.....	48
7	EDGE OR DIFFICULT CASES	48
8	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	51
9	REFERENCES.....	51
	APPENDIX 1: SCDL Codes and Definitions	52
	APPENDIX 2: Annotated Note for SCDL	58
	APPENDIX 3: Abbreviations found in clinical documentation	63

TABLES

Table 1. The color-coding scheme for identifying SCDL mentions	13
Table 2. Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) codes.....	15
Table 3. Annotation of Headers and Titles	23
Table 4. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as d570	37
Table 5. Non-examples of looking after one’s health (text that should not be annotated)	38
Table 6. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as Managing Medications	39
Table 7. Non-examples of Managing Medications (text that should not be annotated).....	40
Table 8. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as Therapy	40
Table 9. Non-examples of Therapy (text that should not be annotated)	40

FIGURES

Figure 1. Diagram of the ICF with the Activity component highlighted	5
Figure 2. The Activities and Participation component of the ICF with the Self-Care & Domestic Life chapters highlighted in orange	7
Figure 3. NIH Clinical Center notes selected for annotation	8
Figure 4. SSA CE and HITMER files selected for annotation	9
Figure 5. Entities and sub-entities of the Self-Care & Domestic Life schema	10
Figure 6. Self-Care & Domestic Life Annotation Schema	10
Figure 7. Workflow of Self-Care & Domestic Life annotation decision logic.....	11
Figure 8. Example Self-Care & Domestic Life Mention and Sub-mentions.	13

1 INTRODUCTION

This work is a product of the Epidemiology and Biostatistics Section of the Rehabilitation Medicine Department, National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center that uses the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001) as a framework to develop analytic tools for clinical natural language processing (cNLP) and to develop vocabularies of function. The interdisciplinary team is by design composed of a diverse set of scientists, including those in health informatics, mathematics, statistics, computer science, public health, and healthcare. The annotation team within the Section that created this guideline included clinical rehabilitation domain experts with backgrounds in occupational therapy, physical therapy, and primary care medicine, as well as individuals with public health and data science expertise.

Creation of the guideline was driven by a use case involving a collaborative agreement with the United States (U.S.) Social Security Administration (SSA) for leveraging cNLP to improve the disability determination process. The research purpose was to develop tools to automate extraction of relevant functional information from electronic health records (EHR) and support medical record review by adjudicators. This guideline aims to standardize self-care and domestic life information that is documented in free-text EHRs and provide a process for annotating this information. These efforts led to creation of a gold standard corpus, which has been used to develop computational models of functioning.

1.1 Use of this Guideline

We recommend that users of this guideline have a good understanding of Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) concepts and domain expertise or access to persons with domain expertise, who can clarify concepts and their semantic representation for annotation in clinical documentation. Though the guideline was developed for manual annotation, it can also be used to develop automated annotation tools for those interested in standardizing the clinical documentation language of SCDL.

The guideline provides a review of the ICF and how functioning at the activity level is conceptualized and identified for annotation. Familiarity with the ICF and its coding scheme is essential. The ICF can be accessed through the [online ICF Browser](#), which outlines ICF categories with code names and descriptions. ICF codes used in this guideline were those available on the ICF browser at the time the guidelines were developed. Users of the guideline need to be aware that the ICF is a working document with ongoing updates potentially adding new codes or modifications to code names and descriptions. Users are advised to check the ICF online browser for the most updated classification and codes.

Appendices are provided as an additional resource for users of the guideline. [Appendix 1](#) provides a full description of the SCDL codes and definitions taken from ICF SCDL domains at the 3-digit code level, and two codes from the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) (National Library of Medicine, 2019) for additional specificity. [Appendix 2](#) provides a synthetic occupational therapy evaluation and discharge note that has

been annotated for SCDL information. [Appendix 3](#) lists abbreviations taken from the SCDL corpus used for annotation, and include additional common abbreviations found in clinical documentation that relate to SCDL.

Users of this guideline are expected to develop their own inter-rater reliability (IRR) measures among annotators and not benchmark their IRR on measures reported in this guideline.

1.2 Introduction to the ICF and conceptualization of function

The ICF was used as a framework to conceptualize functioning and standardize annotation of information at the activities level in EHR using clinical natural language processing (cNLP). The ICF was selected in view of its classification taxonomy of human functioning that has world-wide adoption and provides standardized language of functioning concepts with codes and operational definitions. Using the ICF to establish a common language for describing health and health-related states potential to improve communication between users, permit comparison of data across countries and disciplines, and provide a systematic coding scheme to be used by health information systems.

Functioning is classified on multiple levels from body structures (e.g., cells and organs); to body functions (e.g., mental functions); and functioning at the level of activities and participation (e.g., self-care activities or work participation). An individual's functioning in a specific activity domain is understood as a complex relationship with dynamic interaction among a person's health condition, body structures and functions, and personal and environmental contextual factors (World Health Organization, 2001). Disability is understood as activity limitations or participation restrictions resulting from impairments or environmental barriers. See [Figure 1](#), the ICF scheme with the activity component highlighted, to show the focus of this work is on activity functioning.

Figure 1. Diagram of the ICF with the Activity component highlighted

Functioning at the activity level is recognized as a salient health care outcome for both the individual and for population health (Bickenbach et al., 2023). Health is usually experienced by an individual as the ability to participate in activities that one wants, needs, or is expected to do. Electronic health records are a rich source of functioning information. Clinical NLP (cNLP) has helped to extract big data on human function for use in research that can evaluate intervention outcomes and inform health care policy to benefit individual and population health (Hasan & Farri, 2019). These cNLP efforts, however, have focused primarily on body functions and structures for medical decision support, such as diagnosing diseases and determining interventions (Bickenbach et al., 2023; Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). Extraction of functioning information at the activities level in EHR is much less represented and challenging due to several factors, including a lack of standardization of clinical documentation among providers and inconsistent representation across health systems (Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). As with all components in the ICF, the Activities and Participation component has several domains of functioning as can be seen in [Figure 2](#) that highlights the self-care and domestic life domains.

The ICF uses an alphanumeric system of coding in which the letters b, s, d, and e are used respectively to denote Body Functions, Body Structures, Activities and Participation, and Environmental Factors. All codes in the Activities and Participation component of the ICF begin with a “d.” As Self-Care is the fifth chapter, Self-Care codes begin with “d5,” followed by numbers related to the sub-categories. Domestic Life codes begin with “d6” as it is the sixth chapter and are followed by numbers related to the sub-categories. These letters are followed by a numeric code that begins with the chapter number (one digit), followed by the second level (two digits), and the third and fourth levels (one digit each). Each functioning domain in the Activities and Participation component can be considered a parent category to subcategories nested within broader concepts. In the Activities and Participation component, codes can be added to denote qualifying constructs of capacity (the person’s ability to execute a task) and performance (the actual doing of the task). In addition, more than one code category can be applied to a particular function.

This guideline introduces annotation and coding of SCDL information at the activity level in support of cNLP efforts to automate information extraction in free-text EHR. Though Self-Care and Domestic Life are separate chapters in the ICF, clinical documentation of these concepts is often interwoven. Therefore, we combined the chapters into one domain and schema for annotation purposes. ICF Self-Care and Domestic Life alphanumeric codes used for annotation of SCDL information were done at the second category level beginning with the chapter letter, followed by a 3-digit code (with the first digit representing the chapter number, and the next 2 digits representing the activity).

Figure 2. The Activities and Participation component of the ICF with the Self-Care & Domestic Life chapters highlighted in orange

1.3 Conceptualizing Self-Care & Domestic Life

Self-care activities are commonly referred to as activities of daily living (ADL) and encompass activities a person wants to do, needs to do, or is expected to do to take care of themselves. Domestic life activities are commonly referred to as instrumental activities of daily living (IADL) and encompass activities the person wants to do, needs to do, or is expected to do that support daily life within the home and community and the taking care of others (AOTA, 2020). The ICF provides activity codes that represent both domains of self-care and domestic life activities (World Health Organization, 2001) and are described below. Please see [Appendix 1: SCDL Codes and Definitions](#) for a more complete and comprehensive table that includes ICF codes and their definitions as used in this guideline.

ICF Self-Care codes include washing and drying oneself (d510), caring for one's body and body parts (d520), toileting (d530), dressing (d540), eating (d550) and drinking (d560), and looking after one's health (d570), such as seeing a doctor when one needs to and seeing to one's nutritional needs and comfort.

ICF Domestic Life codes represent the carrying out of domestic and everyday actions and tasks. Areas of domestic life include acquisition of necessities such as acquiring a place to live and caring for one's belongings and space (d610), and acquiring food, clothing and other necessities (d620). Household tasks include preparing meals (d630), doing household tasks and chores in the home (d640), such as household cleaning and repairing and laundry, caring for personal and other household objects (d650), and assisting others (d660).

2 ANNOTATION DATA

Data used for SCDL annotation came from two sources: clinical notes from the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center and health records submitted to the Social Security Administration (SSA) by applicants for work disability benefits.

Health records within the NIH Clinical Center were provided by the NIH Biomedical Translational Research Information System (BTRIS), a resource available to the NIH intramural community, that provides records through limited data sets. The NIH Office of Human Subjects Research Protection (OHRP) determined that research conducted with these limited data sets does not meet the definition of human subjects research pursuant to 45 CFR 46 and OHRP guidance.

The NIH dataset included 61,908 clinical notes from patients at the NIH Clinical Center. Domain experts iteratively filtered document names to narrow the dataset to documents containing information related to self-care or domestic life. The final subset consisted of 37,535 files corresponding to 15 Occupational Therapy (OT) document names, where a document name refers to discipline and type of note (e.g., Occupational Therapy Initial Assessment Note or Interim Note), and a file refers to the actual note itself (e.g., the individual assessment note). Domain experts then identified 300 files to annotate for SCDL functional status (Figure 3).

A second dataset came from the SSA containing Adult Consultative Examination (CE) Reports, and Health Information Technology Medical Evidence Records (HITMER) files. A subset of CE and HITMER files were annotated for information on functioning related to the ICF SCDL domains. (Figure 4).

Figure 3. NIH Clinical Center notes selected for annotation

Figure 4. SSA CE and HITMER files selected for annotation

3 ANNOTATION TOOL

Following a comprehensive review for available annotation tools in 2016-2017, the General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) software tool (Cunningham et al., 2011) was selected, due to its ease of use, portability, and customizable features that adequately met the needs of manual annotation and machine modelling. In addition, GATE did not require that the data be on a repository outside the NIH firewall and did not have a cost associated with open use. GATE is a general text processing framework that includes functionalities commonly found in typical NLP pipelines. While there are some disadvantages to this software, particularly in the realm of co-reference annotations, its utilities were sufficient to satisfy the annotation needs and purpose in creating this guideline.

4 ANNOTATION SCHEMA

Developing the SCDL annotation schema involved exploratory work by health professionals from varied backgrounds to identify components of Self-Care & Domestic Life functional information in clinical free text. Once the major components of SCDL (SCDL entity, Action sub-entity, Assistance sub-entity, and Quantification sub-entity) were determined, attributes and values to each of these components were added to provide additional contextual and/or functional information to the annotations. Figure 5 shows the final framework of the schema. Testing the schema was an iterative process using a quality assurance procedure aimed at achieving satisfactory inter-rater reliability (IRR). IRR, calculated as exact match on mention text spans averaged across 4 annotators, achieved F1-scores of 73.8% on the NIH dataset and 68.0% for the SSA dataset.

Figure 5. Entities and sub-entities of the Self-Care & Domestic Life schema

The SCDL annotation schema, with its entities, sub-entities, attributes, values, and hierarchical coding structure, is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Self-Care & Domestic Life Annotation Schema

Figure 7 shows the sequential steps of coding a mention of SCDL information that begins with coding of SCDL entities, followed by the entities' contextual attributes, then the attributes' values. SCDL mentions, entities, attributes, and values will be defined and described further in the next section.

Figure 7. Workflow of Self-Care & Domestic Life annotation decision logic

4.1 Entities and Mentions

An entity refers to a concept of the information being annotated, and a mention is a textual statement of the underlying entity. In this guideline an entity is the description of what is annotated, and a mention refers to the text annotated.

Six entities make up the SCDL schema: SCDL; Action; Assistance; Quantification; Score Definition; and Instructions/Questions. Action, Assistance, and Quantification are considered sub-entities because they are hierarchically below a SCDL entity and can only occur within it. Definitions of all the entities are provided below.

A **SCDL entity** is a self-contained, well-defined description of self-care or domestic life functional status information. The definition is purposely broad to allow for normal textual variation of SCDL documentation in clinical records. Three types of sub-entities may be present within a SCDL entity: Action, Assistance, and Quantification.

Action sub-entity refers to information about activities contained within the SCDL entity. An Action could be expressed as a verb or verb phrase, a noun or noun phrase, an inflection, a

gerund, or a combination thereof. The key role of an Action sub-entity is to identify the type of activity being done.

Assistance sub-entity refers to information about dependence on another person or object when performing an activity. The key role of an Assistance sub-entity is to identify the level of practical support.

Quantification sub-entity is information related to measurement values of the activity.

Score Definition entity is a standardized assessment of functional status, commonly represented as numerical values that provide semantic interpretation of functional status. The SCDL entity and its sub-entities often refer to numerical values from a scale or as a score to quantify functional status. However, these scales are not part of a SCDL entity, and they are often defined separately in a series of short phrases. Score definition is a standalone entity made up of short phrases that assist in the semantic interpretation of functional status.

Instructions/Questions entity Refers to SCDL information in the form of instructions and questions that contain no actual information related to the patient. Instructions for the provider about how to fill out a form related to the SCDL status of the patient or questions about SCDL where no answer is given would fall into this category.

As explained above, a **mention** is a textual statement that represents the instance of an underlying real-world entity. It is a contiguous span of tokens (a word or punctuation symbol) that makes up a phrase, a simple sentence, or a complex sentence.

Given that the SCDL entity contains three sub-entities (i.e., Action, Assistance, and Quantification), a SCDL mention may contain Action sub-mentions, Assistance sub-mentions, and Quantification sub-mentions. [Figure 8](#) gives an example of a SCDL mention and sub-mentions along with their linguistic roles. In this guideline, a mention will always refer to the representation of an entity or sub-entity.

Patient able to brush teeth every day without set-up only when seated in front of the sink.

Figure 8. Example Self-Care & Domestic Life Mention and Sub-mentions.

As illustrated in Table 1, a specific color-coding scheme to label mentions is used. The color scheme for annotations in GATE is as follows: the entire SCDL mention is highlighted in yellow, the Action mention is highlighted in blue, the Assistance mention is highlighted in red, the Quantification mention is highlighted in green, the Score Definition mention is highlighted in turquoise, and the Instructions/Questions mention is highlighted in magenta.

In this guideline, the following colors are used to illustrate annotations: the entire SCDL mention is highlighted in yellow the text of the Action mention is blue, the text of the Assistance mention is red, the text of the Quantification mention is green, Score Definition mentions are highlighted in turquoise, and Instructions/Questions mentions are highlighted in magenta. Please refer to [Appendix 2: Annotated Note for SCDL](#) for an example of a clinical document fully annotated for the SCDL domain. [Appendix 3](#) can also be used in conjunction as a resource of common abbreviations found in clinical documentation.

Table 1. The color-coding scheme for identifying SCDL mentions

Color Scheme in GATE	Color Scheme in Guideline
Self-care & Domestic Life	Yellow highlight
Action	Blue text
Assistance	Red text
Quantification	Green text
Score Definition	Turquoise highlight
Instructions/Questions	Magenta highlight

4.2 Attributes and Values

The SCDL entity, Action sub-entity, Assistance sub-entity, and Quantification sub-entity all include attributes. Score Definition and Instructions/Questions entities do not include attributes. Attributes refer to specific characteristics or types of SCDL information that have Value codes. Value codes provide additional contextual and/or functional information about the attribute and entity that they are assigned to. Attributes and their Values for each of the entities are described below.

4.2.1 SCDL Entity: Attributes and Values

The SCDL Entity has three attributes: **Type**, **Subject**, and **Timeline**. Attributes of the SCDL entity capture general information about functional SCDL status. Each of these attributes have values and are further defined and described below.

The **Type** attribute refers to the source of a statement. If the statement is an observation from a clinical professional, the **Value** of the Type attribute is **Objective**. If the statement comes from a patient, a relative, etc., then the **Value** of the Type attribute is **Subjective**.

The **Subject** attribute refers to the person whom the statement is about. If the statement is about the patient, the **Value** of the Subject is **Patient**. Otherwise, the **Value** of the Subject is **Other**.

The **Timeline** attribute refers to when an activity occurred. If the activity in the SCDL mention happened before the current health care visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Past**. If the activity described is part of the current visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Present**. If the activity is expected to occur after the visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Future**. This **Future Value** is not annotated for statements from the provider that contain recommendations, goals, etc., unless it is stated that these are met or partially met.

4.2.2 Action Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

The Action sub-entity has two attributes: **SCDL Code** and **Polarity**. Attributes of an Action sub-entity capture the type of activity as well as a person's ability to perform the activity.

The **SCDL Code** attribute consists of seven Self-Care 3-digit ICF codes, six Domestic Life 3-digit ICF codes, and two SNOMED CT codes. We did not include ICF codes of "other specified" or "unspecified" in the SCDL annotation schema due to their ambiguity. [Table 2](#) offers a detailed list of the SCDL codes, code descriptions, and text examples taken from clinical notes. Please see [Appendix 1](#) for a full description of the SCDL codes. The included 3-digit ICF codes were the codes published and available on the ICF browser at the time the guidelines were developed. The WHO continues to add or edit codes on the online browser. Please check the [ICF online browser](#) for the most current version of the classification and codes.

Polarity refers to a person's performance of an activity. If the person can do any part of the activity (from minimal to maximum assistance included), with or without an assistive device,

and/or with no hands-on assist such as verbal prompt, then the polarity attribute of the Action sub-entity is **able**. If the person cannot do the activity or is fully dependent and requiring full physical assist from another person, then the Polarity attribute of the Action sub-entity is **unable**. If the person’s ability cannot be determined (e.g., can sometimes dress by themselves), or the amount, type of assistance, or whether the person needs assistance or not, is also undeterminable, then the Polarity attribute of the Action sub-entity is **unclear**. If documentation indicates the person has difficulty/is limited to perform or complete the activity, then the polarity is **effort**. The value of **no_polarity** Includes observations where ability cannot be discerned, such as “appears well groomed and well dressed,” or “wears glasses.” This includes statements of what the person does not do without any reference as to whether the person can or cannot perform the action, such as “He would rather not do the laundry.” **no_polarity** can also be assigned in cases where the activity is in the future or related to the ICF d570 code and SNOMED CT codes.

Table 2. Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) codes

ICF SCDL Codes	ICF SCDL Code Description	SCDL Action Examples
d510	Washing oneself	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient dependent in sponge baths. • Bathing: Assist needed. • Uses a long towel to be able to reach and dry her back after showering.
d520	Caring for body parts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • She is able to groom herself. • Well-groomed.* • Needs assistance with washing his hair. • He now can stand before the sink to brush his teeth each day.
d530	Toileting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient independent with toileting. • Had difficulty managing zipper of pants for toileting.
d540	Dressing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Began requiring assistance with dressing and undressing. • I can dress myself, it’s just that it takes so long. • Casually dressed.* • Wearing (i.e., splint/glasses**). • Her clothing was appropriate for the weather conditions. • Needed no help changing for exam.
d550	Eating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He had been eating some food orally. • Can feed self after set up. • Is independent with eating. • Self-feeding.

d560	Drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coughing when taking thin liquids. • She also has trouble drinking from a cup.
d570	Looking after one's health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exercise 4 to 5 times a week. • practices yoga once a week. • Doing cardiovascular exercise. • Swimming, biking. • Stretching, breathing techniques. • He drinks two shots of whiskey a day. • She has had two suicide attempts in the past. • He smokes a pack of cigarettes a day. • Patient reports no illegal drug use. • Takes over the counter supplements (e.g., vitamins). • Overdosed on pills. • Engage in substance use. • He is compliant with treatment but remains symptomatic. • I haven't gone to counseling but I talk to my friend who is a preacher. • He consumed caffeine 1 – 2 times a week.
d610	Acquiring a place to live	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pt purchased a house. • Patient has installed a grab bar in the shower. • He became Homeless. • She resides in a shelter.
d620	Acquisitions of goods and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • She relies on a neighbor to buy groceries for her. • He is able to make small purchases on his own.

d630	Preparing meals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occasionally the aide will prepare meals. Able to do some meal preparation herself Using the blender Spread the jam on bread Heating up a pot of water Grinding flour Cut and sauté vegetables Making a mocha Mixing ingredients for breading chicken Follow simply written recipes^{***} Participated in one stovetop activity
d640	Doing housework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> He put away the dishes and ran the dishwasher. The patient helps in household chores with vacuuming and doing his own laundry.
d650	Caring for household objects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> He repaired his own car and does his own home repairs. She mowed the lawn.
d660	Assisting others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> with very young children to take care of. She takes her elderly mother to medical appointments.
No ICF code ****		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Doing household task. Cleaning. Doing household chores. Doing things around the house, etc. Activities of daily living. Instrumental activities of daily living. Self-care activities.
SNOMED CT Code	SNOMED CT Code Name	Example Action
285033005	Ability to manage medication (observable entity) "Manage medication"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate in medication program. Taking medication.
709007004	Compliance behavior to therapeutic regimen "Therapy"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient to be indep in a HEP[^] Continues to participate in counselling sessions with this therapist 2x/week

* Note: Only annotate the actions of grooming and dressing, not provider observations of quality (well-groomed, neatly groomed, casually dressed).

**The action "wearing" refers to ICF d540 with no polarity.

***This action refers to ICF code d630 (Preparing simple meals) and is not to be confused with code b167 (mental function language- reception of written language).

**** Contain SCDL information and are annotated as an Action mention but are too broad a term to be assigned any ICF code.

^Home exercise program

4.2.3 Assistance Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

The Assistance sub-entity has two attributes: **source** and **polarity**. These attributes capture the general level and type of help or support the patient requires to complete an activity.

Source refers to the type of support the person requires to complete an activity. If the support is an adaptive device or equipment such as a sock-aid or a long-handled reacher, then the value of the source attribute is **other**. Adaptive clothing or any non-human assist, such as a service dog or other miscellaneous such as a pill organizer and Foley catheter (assistive device for toileting) can also be classified as **other**.

If another individual is helping the person complete the activity, such as through supervision or some type of physical assistance such as contact guard assist, then the value of the source attribute is **person**.

The source **set_up** is selected when steps need to be taken to prepare for a task to be initiated such as by organizing time, space, and materials.

Lastly, when the Assistance polarity is false (i.e., the word “independent” and derivatives) then select **no_source** attribute.

The Assistance **polarity** refers to any type of help/support the person needs to complete an activity. If a person does require some sort or level of assist or help, the value of the polarity attribute is **true**. If the person does not require any assist or help, then the value of the assistance polarity attribute is **false**. If the level of assistance cannot be assessed from the text, the value of the polarity attribute is **unclear**. There is also an option of **no_polarity** where the assistance polarity is not assigned. Examples of these values are given further down in the guideline.

4.2.4 Quantification Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

Type is the single attribute of the Quantification sub-entity and refers to what is being measured. The values of the Quantification attribute are distance, time, scale, frequency, and other. **Distance** values refer to a measurable length of a SCDL activity. **Time** values refer to a measurable temporal duration. The **scale** value refers to any number representing a patient’s SCDL score. **Frequency** is assigned as a value if the activity occurs or is repeated over a specified interval or unit of time, and **other** is assigned to anything else that can be measured and is related to the SCDL domain.

5 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Annotating a SCDL mention and its sub-entities can be carried out in many ways. It is recommended that annotators approach the task in a top-down fashion: first apply general rules, then apply rules specific to the mention type.

To annotate a health record, an annotator first identifies SCDL mentions, followed by sub-entities (Action, Assistance, Quantification) within each SCDL mention. For each mention or sub-entity, the annotator assigns a value to corresponding attributes. Examples of these values are type = subjective (SCDL mention), source = other (Assistance mention), and polarity = able (Action mention).

Score Definition mentions are identified separately from SCDL mentions and do not contain any sub-entities or attributes. See [Figure 8](#) that illustrates the annotation workflow process.

5.1 Annotate for semantics and not syntax

At times, clinical documentation of SCDL information can be confusing or ambiguous due to the syntax of a phrase or sentence. Mentions of SCDL information are always annotated for their meaning and not their syntax.

5.2 Grammatical and Typographical Errors

Grammatical and typographical errors do occur in clinical documents. When annotating, do not edit the text of the record. If the annotator can understand the text as written and it contains SCDL information, then it should be annotated. See examples of different cases below.

Typographical error example: She showersby herself

With run-on words, only the text of interest is annotated. In the above example, only the string “showers” is annotated as the Action mention.

Misspelling example: Transfer form bed-chair or Able to bursh teeth everyday

Annotate the misspelled word without changing the original text.

5.3 General Guidelines for Annotating Mentions

1. Annotate patient SCDL status, whether in phrases or sentences.
2. Do not include punctuation at the beginning or end of a mention if possible. Annotate the shortest span of text.

Example 1: Pt showers independently (with shower chair and grab bar)

Example 2: Patient has been encouraged to continue with using TheraBand for shoulder strengthening exercises.

Example 3: “I can dress by myself using a dressing stick”.

3. As previously shown in Figure 7, there is a sequence to annotation of the SCDL mention. Annotate the SCDL mention first, then the sub-entities (Action, Assistance, and Quantification), followed by values and attributes. Sub-entities never exist outside a SCDL entity mention.

Example 1: Patient able to brush teeth every day with set-up

1. Annotate SCDL mention: Patient able to brush teeth every day with set-up
2. Next annotate Action mention: Patient able to brush teeth every day with set-up
3. Next annotate Assistance mention: Patient able to brush teeth every day with set-up
4. Next annotate Quantification mention: Patient able to brush teeth every day with set-up

4. A SCDL mention can contain one or more sub-entity.

Example 1: He continues to go to the gym (Action mention only)

Example 2: The patient remains dependent on others (Assistance mention only)

Example 3: Bathing: Assist needed (Contains both Action and Assistance mentions)

5. A SCDL mention can contain the same type of sub-entity mention multiple times.

Example 1: Patient uses bath stool/grab bar when showering/toileting

This SCDL mention has two Action mentions – “showering” and “toileting” – and two Assistance mentions – “uses bath stool” and “grab bar.”

Example 2: does not shower or shave daily

This SCDL mention contains two Action mentions – “shower” and “shave.”

6. Sub-entity mentions can contain other sub-mentions. When the complete phrase of one sub-mention is interrupted by a different sub-mention, double annotation of a word or phrase may be needed.

Example 1: She washes independently her car

The Action mention “washes her car” is broken up with the Assistance mention “independently”. In cases like this, the word that breaks up the Action mention (i.e., “independently”) is included as collateral as part of the Action mention “washes [independently] her car”. The term “independently” is also annotated as an Assistance mention.

7. SCDL mentions never overlap.

8. Score Definition mentions never overlap with each other or with SCDL mentions.
9. At times a longer span of text for a SCDL mention is needed to preserve the mention's meaning.

Example 1: Patient has wife's support as needed. He has been modified independent with toileting using a safety frame due to mobility limitations.

In this example, based upon the context not seen but surrounding the note, the two separate sentences are referring to the action of toileting function and therefore annotated as one SCDL mention. The semantics of the SCDL mention with two sentences are that the patient can toilet on his own using equipment but sometimes requires help from the wife for toileting. In this case annotate:

Wife's support [source=*person*] [polarity=*true*]
Modified independent [source=*other*] [polarity=*true*]
Using safety frame [source=*other*] [polarity=*true*]

5.4 General Guidelines for Attributes and Values

1. All attributes and values should be annotated.
2. Assign an attribute to a sub-entity mention only when information is explicitly stated in the text.

2.1. Assistance mention attribute examples:

Example 1: She is independent in dressing [source=*no_source*] [polarity=*false*]

Example 2: The patient can dress independently without reminders [source=*person*] [polarity=*false*]

2.2. Action mention attributes examples:

Example 1: Can dress without assistive device [scdl subdomain code=*d540*] [polarity=*able*]

The Action mention has an ICF SCDL subdomain code (*d540*) and a polarity of *able* because it is stated that the action is being performed by the patient.

Example 2: She can sometimes dress herself [scdl subdomain code=*d540*] [polarity=*unclear*]

The Action mention has polarity of *unclear* because the level of function cannot be assessed from the text.

3. The polarity value of one attribute does not depend on the polarity value of another attribute.

Example 1: Patient is able to dress without an assistive device [Action polarity=*able*]
[Assistance polarity=*false*]

The Action polarity mention is *able*. This is separate from the Assistance polarity mention which is *false* (meaning the patient is independent and does not require any assistance).

4. If a clinical record states that the functional status of an SCDL activity was “not assessed,” annotate it as a SCDL mention and annotate any Action or Assistance sub-mentions without a polarity attribute (polarity = *no_polarity*).

Example 1: Dressing: not assessed [Action Polarity=*no_polarity*]

5. Attributes capture important information that enrich the SCDL mention. Thus, values assigned to attributes should be derived from the holistic meaning of the SCDL mention, not limited to local syntactical structure.

Example 2: The patient is independent without the use of assistive device except requiring grab bars for toileting [source=*other*] [polarity=*able*]

The long assistance mention is needed to capture the meaning that for toileting the patient is modified independent due to the use of grab bars.

6 SCDL-SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS

6.1 SCDL Sub-entity Mentions

The following are considerations to keep in mind when annotating SCDL mentions.

1. A single complex sentence can have multiple clauses with conjunctions. If it is possible to separate clauses into distinct SCDL mentions that stand on their own and still make sense, then annotate these clauses as different SCDL mentions even when they share the same subject.

Example 1: Examiner observed the patient to be clean, well-groomed and casually and appropriately dressed.

This example includes a sentence that is annotated as three separate SCDL mentions.

2. On the other hand, combine multiple phrases to form a single SCDL mention when they are related and cannot stand on their own. For example, the following is a single SCDL mention since all the phrases relate to the “Bathing” header.

Example 1: Bathing: Level of assistance: Set-up Assistive device: bath stool

- Only annotate headers, titles, and generic programs (e.g., UE dressing, LE dressing, adaptive equipment, smoking status) when there is no Action information in the following text. Do not annotate headers, titles, and generic programs when the subsequent text contains an Action and can stand alone without the header.

Table 3. Annotation of Headers and Titles

Examples of Annotated Headers and Titles	Examples of Headers and Title that are Not Annotated
Toileting: indep	UE dressing: indep but with difficulty reaching overhead to don/doff pullovers, manage tie, collar LE dressing: uses shoe funnel for placing shoes, elastic shoelaces in lieu of needing to bend to tie laces and has sock aide as needed
Upper Body Dressing: Independent	Adaptive Equipment/Strategies: Bathroom Equipment: Bath stool/chair
Smoking status: a pack daily	Smoking status: Current Every Day Smoker-- 1.00 packs/day Types: Cigarettes Smokeless tobacco: Not on file

- Annotate sentences as SCDL mentions when the patient uses an assistive device (e.g., dressing stick) for a SCDL action even when the action is not explicitly stated.

Example 1: Patient uses bath stool

Example 2: Pt relies on sock aid.

- When there is a question and an answer included in the document, annotate the span of text as a SCDL mention with all the sub-entities, attributes, and values as in the example below.

Example 1: Does the patient have the ability to complete their own toileting? YES

Annotations where a question has an answer (meaning the patient was evaluated or they are performing an activity) differ from annotating questions that only include mentions of SCDL activities but are not related to the patient, which are annotated with the Instructions/Questions mention as shown in [Section 6.6](#).

6.1.1 Attributes and Values of the SCDL Sub-entity

The SCDL mention has three attributes: type, subject, and timeline. All three attributes are required for annotation and must be assigned values.

1. Examples of the SCDL **type attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: Upper Body Dressing: Modified independent [*objective*]

Example 2: The patient helps in household chores with vacuuming and doing his own laundry [*subjective*]

NOTE: Assign objective as the type attribute if the source of information on SCDL activities is unclear because such activities could be observed by a clinician during the evaluation or reported by a non-clinician (e.g., self-report).

Example 1: Patient is able to dress himself with assistance [*objective*]

2. Examples of the SCDL **subject attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets:
All attributes of an action need to relate to the abilities of the subject assigned within a mention.

Example 1: The patient cooks at times [*patient*]

Example 2: Her mother does all the cooking [*other*]

Example 3: Patient was raised by his grandmother [*other*]

Example 4: She has one child who is cared for by her maternal grandmother [*other*]

Example 5: Patient said that she was raised primarily by her mother [*other*]

3. Examples of the SCDL **timeline attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: Prior to his admission, he was independent with all self-care activities [*past*]

Example 2: Pt is dependent for lower body dressing, bathing [*present*]

Example 3: Within two weeks pt. will be mod A with lower body dressing [*future*]

6.1.2 Special Cases and Considerations for SCDL Mentions

6.1.2.1 Modal verbs (should, would, could, etc.)

Phrases like the ones below where the information is given with modal verbs (should, would, might) could be annotated as SCDL mentions with **timeline = present** or **timeline = future** depending on the context of the sentence. No polarity will be used for Action and Assistance mentions if in a future mention.

Example 1: She would have minimum difficulty with meal preparation [*present or future*]

Example 2: Pt should be able to prepare simple meals by himself without assistance [*present or future*]

Example 3: Pt should take medications as prescribed [*future*]

Example 4: She would benefit from a transfer tub bench to enable her to sit while showering [future]

6.1.2.2 Annotating for multiple domains within the same project / dataset

It is possible that information on functioning in some SC DL mentions overlaps with information on functioning from other ICF activity chapters such as mobility. In cases like this, it is important to be aware of and differentiate between the kinds of functioning information being annotated and how to annotate it.

Example 1: When getting dressed she has to sit at EOB

In the example above, information on functioning from both the SC DL and the Mobility domain is present. SC DL information is captured in the action of “getting dressed”. Even though the phrase “has to sit at EOB” could be considered a Mobility mention, it is annotated as part of the SC DL mention because this information is needed to classify the action of “getting dressed” with **polarity = effort**. In these instances, mentions relating to different ICF domains can overlap, but the reason for annotation is determined by the schema being utilized.

6.1.2.3 Broad meanings of functional terms

Sentences that are written using terms that are too broad to discern functional ability to a specific SC DL ICF activity code, such as *functional independence* and *independent function*, should not be annotated, even though they may have trigger words like “function”.

Example 1: Patient will increase his physical tolerance/endurance so as to resume independent function in all aspects of his life upon d/c

Example 2: Pt shows improvement in her functional independence

6.1.2.4 Hypothetical information

Do not annotate hypothetical sentences as SC DL mentions. Only annotate SC DL information related to the patient.

Example 1: If I don’t take Prozac I can’t seem to function

In this example, the sentence appears to have information about “taking medication”, but the sentence would not be annotated since it is a hypothetical case. The examples below include bolded words that indicate hypothetical situations.

Example 2: The patient states that **if** he required assistance related to ADLs, he would count on support from his mother or brother

Example 3: He admitted he **would not have passed** a drug test today

Example 4: ...**is viewed** as possessing sufficient judgment to seek medical care **if** needed

Example 5: She said her sleep is better **if** she takes medication

Example 6: He was **uncertain** about whether he has engaged in counseling/psychotherapy

Example 7: He said he is drunk **if** he drinks a case.

Additionally, do not annotate hypothetical questions or patient answers documented in a clinical note that may have “trigger” words for SCDL information. For example, a note may include a question such as “What is the difference between a hat and a coat?” and the patient response is documented as “You wear a hat on your head and put on a coat on your body”. The word “wear” is often annotated as a SCDL mention; however, in this example it is not related to the patient’s SCDL function, but rather it is simply an answer to a hypothetical question in the context of an evaluation.

6.1.2.5 Provider information relating to SCDL information

Do not annotate SCDL information referring to what the provider did or did not do, such as verbal education given to the patient.

Example 1: Instructional/Demonstrative Education: Pt educated on how he can attempt to dress his lower body in bed

Example 2: Verbal Education: Pt was encouraged to continue using his shower chair when taking a shower

However, do annotate recommendations or prognosis information given by the provider related to SCDL annotate as future mentions with **timeline = *future***.

Example 1: Prognosis may improve with psychiatric medication management by a psychiatrist. Abstinence from substances in advised

Example 2: The prognosis for sustained abstinence from use of marijuana with substance abuse treatment at this time is fair

6.1.2.6 Work activities and SCDL mentions

Do not annotate SCDL mentions when the activities are related to work tasks or responsibilities, as work is classified as part of a different component of the ICF.

Example 1: Pt reports he had to wash dishes at his job for 13 hours straight.

Example 2: He works in a hotel and his job involves doing laundry and cleaning the guest rooms.

6.2 Action Sub-Mentions

Action sub-mentions capture local modifiers as part of the Action mention related to ICF or SNOMED CT codes.

1. Do not annotate local modifiers of the Action mention, such as “able to,” “unable to,” “should,” “shouldn’t,” etc. since the primary role of an Action mention is to capture the type of activity. The information provided by the local modifiers is annotated instead via the polarity attribute (i.e., *able*, *unable*, *unclear*, *effort*, or *no_polarity*).

Example 1: Patient able to do the laundry

Only the phrase “do the laundry” is annotated as the Action mention.

2. An Action mention can cover an entire SCDL mention.

Example 1: Wore a Foley catheter

Example 2: Donning and Doffing left BKA prosthetic limb

3. Capturing Action mentions within a SCDL mention can be abstract and open to interpretation because the same ICF subdomain code can apply to a variety of SCDL activities. For example, d570 (Looking after one’s health) can be applied to very different activities such as “go to the gym” or “been sober” (see the first two examples below). Similarly, d630 (Preparing meals) is applicable to the activities described in the last two examples (“making a mocha” and “cutting peppers”).

Example 1: He continues to go to the gym [d570]

Example 2: She has been sober for over 3 years [d570]

Example 3: He worked making a mocha [d630]

Example 4: He worked slowly but meticulously cutting peppers for the meal [d630]

6.2.1 Attributes and Values of the Action Sub-mention

The Action sub-entity has two attributes: SCDL subdomain codes and polarity.

SCDL subdomain codes incorporate all three-digit ICF codes from the Self-Care and Domestic Life chapters of the ICF and two additional SNOMED CT codes for further specifying code d570. The following are examples of the **SCDL subdomain code attribute** with the corresponding code value in square brackets:

Example 1: Patient dependent in sponge baths [d510]

Example 2: Patient independent with toileting [d530]

Example 3: Upper Body Dressing: Independent [d540]

Example 4: Able to do some meal preparation [d630]

Table 2 provides a detailed list of the SCDL ICF codes, their descriptions, and illustrative examples taken from medical records.

The Action polarity attribute corresponds to a person’s ability to perform an action (able, unable, unclear, effort, no_polarity). The following are examples of the **Polarity attribute** value in square brackets:

Example 1: Patient to be able to independently don and doff his customized left wrist splint independently without effort [able]

Example 2: grooming: mod indep - supervision after setup when patient is supine in bed w/raised head of bed [able]

- Example 3:** Patient can **do some microwave cooking** [able]
Example 4: She is unable to help with **household activities** [unable]
Example 5: **Bathing:** Max Assist needed [unable]
Example 6: He is having greater difficulty with **dressing** [effort]
Example 7: The person has to sit EOB to **perform dressing activities** [effort]
Example 8: She is able to minimally **self-feed** [effort]
Example 9: Patient is able to **feed** herself some [effort]
Example 10: making accommodations as needed to complete them, e.g. sitting to **dress lower body** [effort]
Example 11: **Bathing:** Assist needed [unclear]
Example 12: He is mostly independent with **bathing** [unclear]
Example 13: Patient will be able to **self-feed** [no_polarity]

NOTE: ICF code d570 and SNOMED CT codes always have a polarity value of "no_polarity".

6.2.2 Special Cases and Considerations for the Action Sub-entity

6.2.2.1 Future tense

Action mentions written in the future tense, including therapeutic goals for the patient, are assigned a Polarity value of **no_polarity**.

- Example 1:** Patient will be able to **dress** herself by next session [scdl subdomain code=d540] [polarity=no_polarity]

6.2.2.2 Linguistic issues when annotating

SCDL information is always annotated for its semantic meaning. Consider the following examples of annotating the Action word of “dressing”. The semantics are the same – the patient is unable to dress themselves.

- Example 1:** Patient is unable with **dressing** [polarity=unable]
Example 2: Patient is dependent with **dressing** [polarity=unable]

Consider the following examples of annotating the Action word of “eat”. The semantics are the same – the patient ingests only a small amount of food.

- Example 1:** Patient does not **eat** much/a lot [polarity=able]
Example 2: Patient can **eat** a little [polarity=able]

Additional words or phrases sometimes need to be included in annotation to convey an intrinsic meaning about the SCDL action performed by the patient in relation to the context.

- Example 1:** Patient returned to join group **for dessert**

The phrase “for dessert” is annotated because it carries the meaning of “eating” (scdl subdomain code=d550) according to the context in the SCDL mention of eating with others.

Example 2: Complete at least one load of laundry (washing and drying)

In the example above, because of the context, the words “washing” and “drying” are annotated as scdl subdomain code *d640* (doing housework) and NOT *d510* (washing/drying oneself).

Example 3: Wore a Foley catheter

In this example, wearing a Foley catheter means the patient uses this device to perform the task of toileting. Therefore, the whole phrase is annotated with **SCDL Code d530** (Toileting).

6.2.2.2.1 Double negatives

Mentions of “double negative” phrases can cause some confusion. Take the following phrase as an example:

Example 1: He does not take medications other than as prescribed.

This phrase means that the patient is in fact taking prescribed medications. Considering the semantics, or the meaning, the phrase “take medications” would be annotated as the Action mention with **scdl subdomain code = *managing_medication*** and **polarity = *no_polarity***

6.2.2.2.2 Semantics of attributes

In the following examples the same action word has a different value for the polarity attribute because we assign values that represent the meaning of the phrase.

Example 1: She feeds herself

The Polarity of the Action mention “feeds” is able.

Example 2: She cannot feed herself

The Polarity of the Action mention “feed” is unable.

6.2.2.3 Contextual considerations for coding

Words that are relevant for SCDL information may have different meanings depending on the context. For example, the word “clean” is coded differently based on its meaning in the following examples.

Example 1: She will clean the kitchen [scdl subdomain code=*d640*]

Example 2: He cleans himself in the shower [scdl subdomain code=*d510*]

Certain terms may be used among different activity domains, but the meaning is different. In these instances, context provides information about whether the term is relevant to the domain being annotated. For example, consider the term “buttons” in the following examples:

Example 1: The patient used a dressing board for improving her bilateral UE hand use. She had trouble with buttons. However, she demonstrated improvement with snap closures.

Example 2: The patient was able to don cardigan using a dressing stick but had trouble with buttons. However, she did line up buttons with the correct button holes.

The first example “trouble with buttons” is mobility information referring to difficulties with fine hand use and manipulation and part of a different ICF activity domain. In the second example, context provides information that trouble with buttons is in context of a dressing activity that requires buttoning. This example is a SCDL mention. Buttons would be coded as an Action mention [scdl subdomain code=d540] [polarity=effort].

6.2.2.4 Dependency concept and annotation

The word “dependency”, or its derivatives, can have different meanings such as needing an assistive device to perform activities, needing help from another person, a physiological need for medication, or substance use/misuse/abuse. Therefore, when annotating an Action related to the concept of dependency, the variety of ways the word is referred to and used by different disciplines needs to be considered.

Example 1: Dressing: Dependent on a dressing stick [scdl subdomain code=d540] [polarity=able]

In cases where the dependency comes from an assistive device, the polarity of the Action mention will be *able* as the meaning here is that the person uses a dressing stick in order to dress independently (often referred to as “modified independence”).

Example 2: Patient is dependent on someone to cut her food for meals [scdl subdomain code=d630] [polarity=unable]

In cases where the dependency is on another person to perform a SCDL activity, it is understood that the patient is completely unable to perform the Action.

Example 3: Dressing: Dependent [scdl subdomain code=d540] [polarity=unable]

In cases where only the word “dependent” or its synonyms modifies the Action, it is understood the person is unable to perform the Action.

Example 4: The patient requires verbal prompts to initiate brushing her teeth [scdl subdomain code=d520] [polarity=able]

In cases where the patient only requires verbal prompts to perform the Action, it is understood that the person has the physical capacity to complete the Action.

Example 5: He is insulin dependent and monitors his blood sugar regularly [scdl subdomain code=d570] [polarity=no_polarity]

In cases where dependency relates to a medical condition, such as dependent on prescribed medication, it is not annotated as it not related to a SCDL activity. Example 5 does contain an Action that is separate from the dependency, though, and so this Action will be annotated and assigned a SCDL code.

Example 6: He has a long history of alcohol dependence but has been in recovery for 6 months [scdl subdomain code=d570] [polarity=no_polarity]

In cases where dependency is on substances, the word “dependence” is included as part of the Action mention as it provides information related to taking care of oneself.

6.2.2.5 Set up of an activity

Setting up an activity, such as preparing time, space, and materials ahead of time to perform an activity, is not part of the codes defined in the ICF for the Self-Care and Domestic Life chapters and therefore is not considered when coding for SCDL Actions. (ICF codes that include set up are included in a separate ICF chapter). SCDL Codes refer to actions the person takes *after* set up.

The following examples show how SCDL actions are understood to be performed independently after set up, therefore annotated with **polarity = able**

Example 1: Patient requires setup for meal prep [scdl subdomain code=d630] [polarity=able]

Example 2: Once set up the patient is able to do meal prep [scdl subdomain code=d630] [polarity=able]

Example 3: Patient is able to do meal prep after set-up [scdl subdomain code=d630] [polarity=able]

Example 4: Participate in meal prep with setup [scdl subdomain code=d630] [polarity=able]

6.2.2.6 Multiple actions for one code

For two different action mentions that refer to a single task, annotate the two Action mentions together.

Example 1: Donning and Doffing left BKA prosthetic limb [d540]

Example 2: Putting on and taking off his pants [d540]

Example 3: Washing and folding the laundry [d640]

Example 4: Washing and drying her hair [d510]

6.2.2.7 Actions with multiple possible codes

When an Action mention is not specific enough to assign one SCDL code or when more than one SCDL code could apply, annotate the action but do not assign any SCDL codes. Examples below show the different possible ways actions could have been interpreted and coded.

Example 1: He does all the household chores (e.g., d630 d640)

Example 2: She is always doing things around the house (e.g., d630 d640, d650)

Example 3: He does not keep himself clean (e.g., d510, d520, d530, d570)

Example 4: He will use the restroom on his own (e.g., d520, d530)

6.2.2.8 Double coding of ICF codes

The only Action mention that is double-coded is the term “drink” or its derivatives. “Drink” is annotated twice when it is used with alcohol. As shown in the following mention of “drinking whiskey”, the word “drinking” is annotated with two different ICF codes – d560 (drinking) and d570 (looking after one’s health).

Example 1: drinking whiskey [scdl subdomain code =d560]

Example 2: drinking whiskey [scdl subdomain code =d570]

6.2.3 SCDL Codes with Special Consideration

6.2.3.1 ICF Code d660 “Assisting others”

Phrases with terms such as “raising” or its synonyms that refer to another person taking care of the patient (or another person) are annotated as SCDL mentions with the Action mention annotated as scdl subdomain code = **d660** and **Type = other**. There are no Assistance mentions to be annotated in these kinds of examples.

Example 1: Raised by grandmother [SCDL Code=d660] [Type=Other]

Example 2: He was raised by his grandparents [SCDL Code=d660] [Type=Other]

Example 3: She has one child who is cared for by her paternal grandmother [SCDL Code=d660] [Type=Other]

Example 4: She was raised primarily by her mother [SCDL Code=d660] [Type=Other]

Example 5: He reported that he was raised primarily by his mother [SCDL Code=d660] [Type=Other]

6.2.3.2 ICF Code d570 “Looking after one’s health”

ICF Code d570 requires specific attention in this guideline as it is quite broad. It is defined in the ICF as, “Ensuring physical comfort, health and physical and mental well-being, such as by maintaining a balanced diet, and an appropriate level of physical activity, keeping warm or cool, avoiding harms to health, following safe sex practices, such as using condoms, getting immunizations and regular physical examinations.” (World Health Organization, 2001). In essence, this code is referring to measures the person does to, or for, oneself or plans to do in the future (i.e., exercising, taking prescribed medications, etc.). It is not referring to what a healthcare provider has done or plans to do, what goals providers set, or descriptions of what the provider said in specific therapy sessions.

Action mentions of ICF code d570 can be quite lengthy due to the broad nature of the code that describes behavior and includes an awareness of the need for the behavior. For example, in the SCDL mention, “she works a double shift although it may be detrimental to her health” the Action sub-mention (noted in blue font) is quite long but the whole phrase is needed to capture the action of working the double shift even though the person knows it will negatively affect her health.

The d570 code is the only SCDL code where negation is annotated as part of the Action if it relates to suicide, substance use including using recreational or illegal drugs, or any type of alcohol use. The negation of therapy or prescription medication is not annotated unless it has to do with non-compliance. Examples of such mentions include: “denies using alcohol”, “has never had a suicide attempt”; “has not been taking her prescribed blood pressure medication”.

The following sections provide more specific information of annotation within the d570 code of taking care of one’s health including how SCDL information referring to the use or misuse of substances is handled, and the use of SNOMED CT codes to add specificity. The d570 and SNOMED CT codes are always annotated with a No Polarity value to avoid judgement of behaviors that may be beyond a person’s control or are due to social determinants of health (e.g., not taking prescribed medications due to lack of finances or health insurance coverage).

6.2.3.3 Proxy terms in annotation

Proxy terms that are a co-reference to an Action mention can be annotated and assigned the Action code it refers to. For example, the word “use”, or its synonyms, can be used as a proxy when referring to alcohol and drug use and can be annotated as a SCDL mention. These proxy terms are most often encountered in mentions referring to substance use, misuse, or abuse including illegal drugs, alcohol, and nicotine. Mentions including the use, or denial of use, are both annotated.

Example 1: “The patient suggests that she first used alcohol when she was in elementary school. Her peak use appears to have been daily since the age of 20 to 28 and that she had last used approximately one week prior”.

This example is annotated as three mentions that show how the word “use” is annotated.

1st Action mention: The patient suggests that she first used alcohol when she was in elementary school

When the word “use” refers to alcohol and drug use, both the words “use” and “alcohol” should be annotated together as part of the Action mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

2nd Action mention: Her peak use appears to have been daily since the age of 20 to 28

When we encounter the word “use” by itself and it is related to use of alcohol and drugs, the word “use” is annotated by itself as the Action mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

3rd Action: She had last used approximately one week prior

In this case even though the word “use” is by itself, it is related to use of alcohol, and the patient was actually using it. In these cases, include the word “had” as part of the mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**). The word “last” is not of interest but considered collateral information that is unavoidable in annotation since it is in the middle of an annotated mention.

Example 2: She used benzodiazepines for a year in the past, and has not used it since 2015.

Similarly, Example 2 can be divided into two SCDL mentions with their respective Action mentions:

1st Action mention: She used benzodiazepines for a year in the past

The word “use” refers to taking a type of drugs. Annotate the word “use” and what is being used, “benzodiazepines”, together as part of the action mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

2nd Action mention: has not used it since 2015

In this case the word “use” is by itself, is related to use of drugs, but the patient is actually not using the drug. In cases like these, include words of negation such as “has not”, “denies” etc., as part of the mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

Example 3: The patient revealed that he first used alcohol at the age of 16 and was using daily for about three years with his last use being approximately two weeks ago.

Example 3 can be divided into three SCDL mentions with their respective Action mentions:

1st Action mention: The patient revealed that he first used alcohol at the age of 16

The word “used” is next to the word “alcohol”. Annotate the terms “used alcohol” together as part of the Action mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

2nd Action mention: was using daily for about three years

Verbs such as “perform” and “does” are annotated when attached to Action mentions. Therefore, annotate the word “was” as part of the Action (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

NOTE: Another example includes “was sober”.

3rd Action: his last use being approximately two weeks ago

In this case the word “use” is annotated on its own as there is nothing else in the mention that can be annotated as an Action sub-mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

Example 4: The patient stated that he tried cocaine once at the age of 20 and that he has never tried any other substances since then

1st Action mention: The patient stated that he tried cocaine once at the age of 20
The word “tried” has the same meaning as “used” and is annotated as part of the Action mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

2nd Action mention: he has never tried any other substances since then
In this case, the phrase “tried any other substances” is related to use of drugs but the patient is actually not using the drug. As with Example 2, indicate negation by including the words “has never” as part of the mention (**SCDL Code = d570** and **Polarity = No Polarity**).

NOTE: Other examples include “denies using”.

Example 5: Stated that his mother helps set up his medications in a pill box but that he takes them on his own

In this example “takes them” is the proxy term referring to taking medications and is annotated with **SCDL code = Manage Medications**.

6.2.3.4 Smoking

Smoking is coded as d570. The Action mention can be a verb such as “smoking” or could be the noun “smoker”. The substance smoked is not annotated.

Example 1: smokes cigarettes

Example 2: marihuana smoker

Example 3: smokes one half pack of cigarettes

Only include the substance the person smokes as part of the Action mention in the case of negation such as “do not/does not”.

Example: does not use alcohol, smoke cigarettes, or use other drugs

6.2.3.5 Suicide

Mentions of suicide are annotated if referring to an action such as an attempt or denial of a suicidal attempt. Having suicidal ideations or plans are thoughts and not actions, therefore are not annotated in this domain.

Example: Past records show 2 unsuccessful suicide attempts. Currently no suicidal intent or plans.

6.2.3.6 SNOMED CT Codes

To better represent more specific activity information related to the d570 code, we added two SNOMED CT codes to the annotation schema that describe management of medication and therapeutic intervention. The SNOMED CT codes are included in the schema as **Manage Medications** and **Therapy**.

Manage Medications (SNOMED CT Code 285033005 - “Ability to manage medication”) refers to anything related to compliance with medications such as the ability to store medications, obtain medications, taking the medications, etc. Manage Medication is annotated if the person is taking the medications prescribed by a healthcare provider or taking non-prescription medications as directed such as over the counter analgesics (e.g., Tylenol, Ibuprofen), cough syrups, etc. Annotate the mention of medication without the reason for taking it (see examples in [Table 6](#)). This category also includes the mismanagement of medication (i.e., forgetting to take medication).

NOTE: Exceptions to the above include:

- Taking supplements; using alternative medicine; and abuse of medication. These exceptions are assigned the d570 code.
- Medications taken in hospital as inpatient and during surgeries and procedures are not annotated.

Therapy (SNOMED CT Code 709007004 - “Compliance behavior and therapeutic regime”) covers non-pharmacological therapies such as:

- Drug rehabilitation
- Physical therapy
- Occupational therapy
- Cognitive behavior modification therapy
- Psychological therapy/counseling
- Anger management

As with the code of “Manage Medication”, only annotate the mention of the patient participating in therapy, not the reason why (see examples in [Table 8](#)).

NOTE: The following codes are always annotated as an Action sub-mention with No Polarity.

- d570;
- Manage Medications;
- Therapy.

The following tables (Tables 4-9) provide examples seen in clinical records with the rationale for annotation decisions for when or when not to code Actions relating to the d570, Manage Medications, and Therapy codes.

Table 4. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as d570

Examples of Looking After One’s Health (d570)	Reason for Annotating
She has had a previous suicide attempt	Suicidal actions are annotated as indicate risks to health.
She is one half to one pack per day smoker She smokes one half to one pack per day	“Smoker” is an example of an action (commonly a verb) being written as a noun. The semantics are the same as in the second sentence so annotated similarly.
He denies using any street drugs Use of alcohol	Annotate “behaviors” that indicate avoiding or denying risks to health. Annotate any mentions of alcohol use or misuse, or abuse.
She denies any alcohol use She drinks a six-pack of beer a day	Any reference to drug or alcohol use is annotated whether someone is using, not using or denies using. The word “drinks” when related to alcohol consumption is coded d570 (In this case, the word “drinks” is also annotated as ICF code d560).
Her tendency to take a double shift knowing that there will be a detrimental impact on her comfort and health status	The longer text span is needed for clarity as has implications for how one takes care of themselves.
There is concern with how she is managing this pain	Pain management is part of being aware of the need and doing what is required, following medical advice etc.
Implement joint protection and energy conservation principles	Preventative measures to take care of one’s health and ensure comfort.
He was going to AA for his alcohol dependency problems	Support groups not specifically for therapy purposes are annotated as d570 and not Therapy code
Patient was well nourished Patient takes a multivitamin daily	This suggests the person is taking care of self
she admitted herself to hospital (or name of the hospital)	Person is actively looking after his/her health
He has been treated with medications and checks his finger glucose regularly	Passive voice from a provider perspective is not annotated. Only annotate what the patient is actively doing.

Examples of Looking After One's Health (d570)	Reason for Annotating
I went to hospital	This is an example of an active voice suggesting patient took his or her own action.
He abused prescribed medication/over the counter medications	Abusing medication refers to not looking after one's health (not to mismanaging medication)

Table 5. Non-examples of looking after one's health (text that should not be annotated)

Non-Examples of Looking After One's Health	Reason for NOT Annotating
Teach pt. benefits of hot/cold modalities, stretching, and adaptive or modified strategies. The patient was educated in hot/cold modalities, gentle range of motion and stretch exercises	Don't annotate what the clinician describes they did in therapy or plans to do in future treatments. Do not annotate education given by the provider.
I was treated/received treatment in hospital for my pneumonia	This is not an active action on the part of the patient. Passive voice.
He has already begun treatment.	Too broad
She has never had counseling and group therapy. Never been to physical therapy or had an epidural He has had no psychiatric care and no history of psychiatric hospitalization. The patient denied having attending counseling	Do not annotate treatment or therapeutic care that the person has not had or used
She said that her sleep varies and that she never feels rested. She is obese (or weight related statements) She lost about 45 pounds in the last year	These are examples of conditions and fall within Body Functions as b-codes.
Close patient follow-up	Too ambiguous to annotate
Identify at least 1 topic of interest related to self-management in context of OT self-	Therapist goals for the patient are not annotated even if they relate to SCDL.

Non-Examples of Looking After One's Health	Reason for NOT Annotating
management group in order to promote active engagement in health management.	
Craving for alcohol	Craving is body function in the ICF
Currently denies any suicidal ideation.	Suicidal ideation, intent, or plan are not considered actions. These are thoughts.
He was taken to hospital	Passive action

Table 6. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as Managing Medications

SNOMED Code 285033005: Managing Medication	
Examples	Reason for Annotating
is currently on medication Prazosin at bedtime, Gideon 60 mg a day, Buspirone 10 mg twice a day and Paxil.	The provider is saying what medications the patient is taking. Assumption is that the patient is taking these as prescribed.
He takes Tylenol He takes Meloxicam	The mention does not need to capture why the person is taking prescribed or non-prescribed medications, only that the person takes it. The action is what the person is doing.
her blood pressure was 190/100+, but she is not taking any antihypertensive medication	Body Functions such as blood pressure or sleep are not included in the SCDL mention even when they provide the “why” and context to illustrate the importance of the medication. “Not taking medications” is annotated because it reflects the person should take medication but does not
reported that she takes the following medications:	Annotate “takes” as Action and do not annotate the list of medications in the mention.
He resumed his medication after surgery and he just finished two days ago	Words such as “finished”, “stopped”, “quit” are one-word actions that can be annotated if referring to medications, drugs, or alcohol cessation.
Patient does not take his prescribed medications	Shows evidence of medication noncompliance

Table 7. Non-examples of Managing Medications (text that should not be annotated)

Non-Examples of Managing Medications	Reason for NOT Annotating
was diagnosed with dementia within the recent past and starting on medication to slow the progression of his symptoms.	The phrase "starting on medication" is a passive voice statement.
She was on OxyContin immediately after her hip surgery. He has been treated with medications for his high blood pressure.	Do not annotate medicine taken in hospital as inpatient and during surgeries and procedures.
He is given his medications which his wife manages on a regular basis.	This action mention falls under d660 (assisting others in health maintenance)
She takes no medication for pain. Patient does not take any psychotropic medications	Do not annotate medication that the person does not take but do annotate medication if it is to do with compliance related issue
I hope they get me on a medication that works My main goal is to improve dressing with less risk of falling	Hypothetical situation
He is currently prescribed medication by his neurologist to help slow down the progression of his symptoms	Don't know if the person is taking the medications prescribed

Table 8. Examples of SCDL Action mentions that are annotated as Therapy

SNOMED CT Code 709007004: Therapy	
Examples	Reason for Annotating
She had occupational therapy for fabrication of a customized splint for pain management	Therapy for a particular purpose related to health
He was seeing a counselor for his drug addiction	Counseling for a particular purpose related to health

Table 9. Non-examples of Therapy (text that should not be annotated)

Non-Examples of Therapy	Reason for NOT Annotating
The patient continues to have treatment in outpatient treatment facility and is currently on medication.	Too vague. Treatment not specified. Need more context.

She was admitted for drug rehabilitation	Too general and not active voice. Drug rehabilitation may include therapy but can also include pharmacology and other interventions.
1234567 Psychiatric Therapy Individual 8901234 Intervention and Counseling on Cessation of Tobacco Use 5678901 Physical Therapy: Session Segments, 15 Minutes	This is a billing statement and listing what sessions the person went to. No functional information.
He has been hospitalized one occasion for evaluation and treatment of psychiatric problems	Too general and not active voice
He has never been hospitalized for psychiatric reasons and has never participated in outpatient psychiatric or psychological treatment services	Do not annotate therapy or treatments the patient has never done or participated in when the context shows this has nothing to do with health compliance or recommendations
His son stated that he has an appointment with the psychiatrist tomorrow	Use of passive voice.

6.2.3.7 Mentions of medication

The SCDL Code of Managing Medications is applied when there is an indication that the patient is actively taking medication. However, there are a variety of ways that taking medication may be documented that indicates an active participation on the part of the patient. There needs to be an indication of the patient taking the medication, as opposed to just a list of the medications that the patient is prescribed.

Annotation for this code includes terms that can be considered proxies for the action of taking medications. The name or type of medication taken is not annotated as part of the action mention but included in the SCDL text span. For example, in the SCDL mention of “the patient is taking medication as prescribed”, the action “is taking” refers to taking medications.

Other phrases indicating that the patient is taking medication may include: “is on” (drug name); “use of” (drug name); a report of the patient participating in a medication/drug trial; patient reports drug side effects or whether medication helped or medication did not help; medical conditions being “controlled with” medication. The following examples provide some guidance of when and how to annotate for the code of Managing Medications.

Example 1: She reported she is on antidepressant medication

Example 2: The patient has a history of emphysema over the past 11 years. He is on Pro Air every four to six hours as needed, Dulera twice a day as needed, Albuterol nebulizer three to four times a day

Example 3: she reported the use of Flexeril (10 mg TID), Cymbalta (60 mg), Gabapentin (300 mg TID), Melatonin (10 mg), and Plaquenil

Example 4: she feels she is doing well with the addition of Amlodipine alone

Example 5: The patient has a history of hypertension. It is controlled with medication

6.3 Assistance Sub-Mention

An Assistance mention captures local modifiers that indicate the level of dependence on either a device or a person when performing SCDL activities.

Example 1: She does not require the use of an assistive device

6.3.1 Attributes and Values of the Assistance Sub-mention

The Assistance sub-mention has two attributes: **source** and **polarity**. Both attributes should always be annotated.

Source has four values: **person** (another person provides the assistance); **other** (the use of adaptive devices/equipment); **set_up** (steps taken to prepare for a task such as by organizing time, space, and materials); and **no_source** (selected when the polarity is false).

Polarity has four values: **true** (the person *does* require or receive assistance); **false** (the person *does not* need or receive assistance); **unclear** (the person *may or may not* need or receive assistance), and **no_polarity** (selected when the timeline attribute of the SCDL mention is “Future”).

The following are examples of SCDL mentions highlighted in yellow with the Assistance sub-mention highlighted in red font followed by assistance Values in square brackets.

Assistance: source attribute and [values] examples:

Example 1: The patient remains dependent on others [person]

Example 2: Patient uses bath stool when showering [other]

Example 3: meal preparation tasks with set-up [set_up]

Example 4: Patient is independent with cooking [no_source]

Example 5: Bathing: Assist needed [no_source]

Assistance: Polarity attribute and [Values] examples:

Example 1: Bathing: Assist needed [true]

Example 2: Grooming: Independent [false]

Example 3: Dressing: Mostly Independent [unclear]

Example 4: Patient will use shower chair [no_polarity]

1. When an Assistance mention is the only sub-mention present within a SCDL mention, annotate the context or heading as part of the SCDL mention, even though it may not provide functional information.

Example 1: Supine to sit: Moderate Assist [source=person]

2. Assistance mentions with the following terms are assigned **polarity** with a value of **true** and **source** with a value of **person**:
 - Total assistance (or Total assist)
 - Maximal assistance (or Max assist)
 - Moderate assistance (or Mod assist)
 - Minimal assistance (or Min assist)
 - Contact guard assist (CGA)
 - Supervision
 - Verbal Prompting/orienting/cues
 - Relying on another person (family, staff, etc.)
 - Encouragement from others (staff, family etc.).
 - Needs help
3. Assistance mentions with the following terms are assigned **polarity** with a value of **true**, but the **source** value is **no_source**:
 - With assistance
 - Assistance needed
 - Assist
 - With assist
 - Assist needed/needs assist
 - Dependent
4. Assistance mentions with the following terms are assigned **polarity** with a value of **true** and **source** value is **other**:
 - Modified independence

Note: Modified independence usually means the person is using some type of assistive device to complete an activity but can also be broader and include modification of the activity itself – such as no longer wearing socks as unable to don or doff them, or even needing help sometimes from another person due to fluctuations in functioning due to a health condition.

6.3.2 Special Cases and Considerations for Assistance Mentions

6.3.2.1 Considering verb tense

Text written in the future tense is annotated as **no_polarity**. This is a general principle that applies to Assistance sub-mention. Additionally, in past or present SCDL mentions, qualifying words such as “with”, “without”, “use”, “requires”, etc. are included in the Assistance sub-mention. However, in future SCDL mentions, these words would not be included in the Assistance sub-mention because the activity has not yet occurred, and the future is considered uncertain.

Example of future mention: Will participate in meal prep with setup [polarity=no_polarity]
[source=set_up]

6.3.2.2 Variability of polarity and source

The following examples illustrate the variability of the polarity and source attributes for Assistance mentions.

Only Polarity selected:

Example 1: He takes his medication every morning **without reminders** [polarity=*false*]
[source=*no_source*]

Only Source selected:

Example 2: Will Participate in meal prep with **setup** [polarity=*no_polarity*] [source=*set_up*]

Example 3: He does not have any **adaptive equipment at home** [polarity=*no_polarity*]
[source=*other*]

No Polarity or Source selected

Example 3: Patient will be **independent with feedings** [polarity=*no_polarity*]
[source=*no_source*]

6.3.2.3 The set up value

The *set_up* value of the Assistance mention has many variations related to the span of text that needs to be captured. The text span can vary from the word “set up” to complete phases within the SCDL mention.

Example: Once in the chair, she was **set up** with her breakfast, which she began to eat **once the French toast was cut up**

In this previous example the phrase “once the French toast was cut up” has the intrinsic meaning of the activity being set up and therefore annotated.

6.3.2.4 Complementary Assistance mentions

In cases where two Assistance mentions complement one another, annotate them separately as in the example below.

Example 1: Self-Feeding: **Dependent, needs finely cut food**

In this case, annotate the Assistance mention “Dependent” with polarity = *true* and source = *no_source*. As a separate Assistance mention, annotate “needs finely cut food” with polarity = *true* and source = *set_up*.

Example 2: **Modified independent with toilet safety frame**

In this case, even though the phrase “with toilet safety frame” is the reason why the patient is classified as being “Modified independent”, annotate both phrases separately and both with source = *other* and polarity = *true*.

6.3.2.5 Annotating assistive devices

Mentions of an assistive device a patient is given or owns without any information about whether the person actually uses the device is annotated. In these cases, annotate with **source = other** and **polarity = no_polarity**. If an assistive device or adaptive piece of equipment is mentioned under the “Plan” and “Goals” sections, then it infers that the item is provided by a health practitioner, such as an OT to support patient’s engagement in SCDL, but not necessarily used unless the Goal or Plan is met during the visit.

Example 1: Pt has a shower seat with grab bars in his bathroom [source=other] [polarity=no_polarity]

Example 2: Patient was provided with a sock aid to help with lower body dressing [source=other] [polarity=no_polarity]

Example 3: She has a tub/shower in her bathroom with a shower chair and handheld shower; no grab bars [source=other] [polarity=no_polarity]

Example 4: Pt was not interested in a reacher or long-handled shoehorn to reduce her bending when dressing her for lower body [source=other] [polarity=no_polarity]

6.3.2.6 Co-referencing of assistance polarity

In some SCDL mentions, there may be more than one assistance mention as to the use or non-use (i.e., with or without) of some type of assist. As in the example below, the term “without” refers to no need for either assistance or adaptive equipment. In cases like these, the two Assistance mentions are annotated with the same Polarity since the meaning is that the person performs SCDL activities without assist and without adaptive aids.

Example 1: She is able to manage self-cares and household activities without assist or adaptive aids

- Assistance mention “without assist” [source=no_source] [polarity=false]
- Assistance mention “adaptive aids” [source=other] [polarity=false]

6.3.2.7 Unclear Assistance Polarity

The polarity of an Assistance mention is unclear if there is variability in the description. These Assistance mentions are annotated with **source = no_source** and **polarity = unclear**.

Example 1: Feeding is relatively independent once she is set up

Example 2: She is mostly independent in dressing

Example 3: He is able to dress with or without adaptive equipment

Example 4: She is sometimes assisted in all self-care

6.3.2.8 Capturing Independent functioning

In some instances, the person needs some level of assistance to perform a task independently, such as by using adaptive equipment or needing set up. In these cases, annotate the word “independent” along with the other assistance mention, no matter the length of the text needed, and use the corresponding attributes and values.

Example 1: She uses the shower chair provided in her bathroom when bathing but is otherwise independent with bathing

Annotate “uses the shower chair provided in her bathroom when bathing but is otherwise independent” as a single Assistance mention with attributes of **source** = *other* and **polarity** = *true*.

Example 2: Per pt. report he is independent with eating after being told where items are located and by feel

Annotate “independent with eating after being told where items are located” as a single Assistance mention with attributes of **source** = *set_up* and **polarity** = *true*.

Note: In the example above, the person is blind and being told where the items are located is considered a verbal set up because the person is verbally-oriented to where food is located on their plate.

In other instances, when the person is independent in performing a task and the text also states there is no need for an assistive device, then we annotate two different Assistance mentions.

Example 3: she was independent with ADL with no assistive devices in her home

The first Assistance mention here is “independent” with attributes of **source** = *no_source* and **polarity** = *false*. The second Assistance mention is “with no assistive device” with attributes of **source** = *other* and **polarity** = *false*.

6.4 Quantification Sub-Mention

A Quantification mention captures information only related to measurement of the action of a SCDL activity, which may include modifiers such as adjectives, adverbs, mathematical operators, and units of measurement.

6.4.1 Attributes and values of the Quantification Sub-Mention

The Quantification sub-mention has a single attribute: Type. The **type** attribute consists of five Values: **Distance** (the length of space taken to complete an activity); **Frequency** (the measurement of repetition, or the number of occurrences of a repeating event, over a given interval or unit of time); **Scale** (a score or value contained within a Score Definition); **Time** (the duration over which an activity occurs), and **other** (any other form of measurement that is not captured in the first four values). The Type attribute is mandatory for annotation.

Quantification information related to action mentions can be represented by less precise and quantifiable terms. For example, Frequency can include terms such as “at times”, “occasionally”, “sometimes”, “always”, “never”, “regularly”, “one time”, “daily”, “every week”,

etc. Time may include terms that denote a time component of duration, such as “chronic” often understood as 3 months or more. Alternative terms for Other may include amounts such as “a little”, “a lot”, etc. In cases where an annotation decision of a quantification mentions is uncertain, it should be annotated.

Examples of the Type attribute with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: He is only able to mow the lawn about 30 feet before he fatigues [distance]

Example 2: She cooks meals about 3 x a week [frequency]

Example 3: The patient cooks meals at times [frequency]

Example 4: She has undergone several therapy sessions [frequency]

Example 5: NIHFA OT Score (6-24): 12/24, as patient needs some assist or supervision to perform his ADL each day [scale]

Example 6: NIHFA OT Score (6-24): 23 [scale]

Example 7: Chronic use of alcohol [time]

Example 8: It took the patient 2 hours to get dressed [time]

Example 9: Able to wash/dry 75% of body surface [other]

Example 10: He stated that he participated in a few months of outpatient therapy, about 6 sessions [other]

Example 11: She can only eat a little of her food [other]

The following are **NOT** considered Quantification but are captured as part of the SCDL mention:

Example 1: He began smoking at age 10 (age is not Quantification)

Example 2: She stopped her medication on 12/21/30 (a date or point in time is not Quantification)

6.4.2 Special Cases and Considerations for Quantification Mentions

The word “about” is included in Quantification mentions as it indicates an approximate measure, such as in examples 1 and 10 above.

6.4.2.1 Annotation of Scores

In Examples 5 and 6 above, the range of the full available score is not annotated as a quantification. However, the score of the patient is annotated. Only the scale value that refers to any number representing a patient’s SCDL score is annotated.

6.4.2.2 Annotation of Frequency

When a SCDL mention includes multiple Quantification mentions, such as a time component and a frequency component, that are clearly separated and delimited in the text, annotate each Quantification mention separately.

Example 1: Use the recumbent bike for 15-20 minutes once a week [time] [frequency]

If there is no space between components still annotate separately as in the example below where “15-20min” refers to time and “/day” refers to frequency.

Example 2: Use the recumbent bike for 15-20min/day [time] [frequency]

6.5 Score Definition Mention

The Score Definition mention is a score or scale that serves as a reference or definition for the scale values captured in Quantification mentions. Score Definition is a unique mention and as such is annotated separately from the SCDL mention and its sub-mentions. Annotate the Score Definition at each occurrence in the text. The following is an example of a Score Definition mention.

Example 1: Including UE dressing, LE dressing, Grooming, Eating, Toileting, Bathing; Scale of 1-4 (1 –total dependence, 2=requires person assistance, 3= requires adaptive device, 4= total indep (this is not standardized and is very subjective) scores range from 6-24.

6.6 Instructions/Questions Mention

The Instructions/Questions mention contains SCDL information in the form of either instructions or questions from templated records where there is no actual information related to the patient. For example, instructions for the provider about how to fill out a form related to the SCDL activities of the patient, or questions about SCDL where no answer is given would fall into this category.

Example 1: Describe the Patient's abilities and limitations in performing activities of daily living.

Example 2: Was an assistive device used for showering, toileting, dressing, eating, and drinking? If so, what are they?

6.6.1 Special Cases and Considerations for Instruction/Question Mentions

6.6.1.1 Annotating Questions with Responses

If the note includes the provider's answer to a question, annotate both the question and answer as one SCDL mention if the provider's answer is brief without specific SCDL information.

Example 1: Please describe whether the patient does all the housecleaning and cooking. If not, how much does he/she do and who does the rest?
Friends; family

Example 2: Describe whether the patient regularly cares for his/her own personal needs, such as dressing and bathing.
Yes

7 EDGE OR DIFFICULT CASES

1. When SCDL mentions can be annotated from the perspective of either the patient or another individual (such as a family member, friend, provider, etc.), then the subject should be the patient, and the sub-mentions should be captured as they relate to the patient.

Example 1: She relies on family member for assistance with meals and shopping

In this example, the entire phrase is annotated as a SCDL mention.

- type = *subjective*
- subject = *patient*
- timeline = *present*

The phrase “**relies on family member for assistance**” would be the Assistance mention with attributes:

- source = *person*
- polarity = *true*

The Action mentions “**meals**” and “**shopping**” are annotated under ICF codes d630 and d620, respectively.

- The polarity of both Actions = *unclear*

Example 2: She is fed by her son

In this example, the entire phrase is annotated as a SCDL mention.

- type = *subjective*
- subject = *patient*
- timeline = *present*

The phrase “**by her son**” would be the Assistance mention with attributes.

- source = *person*
- polarity = *true*

The Action mention “**fed**” is annotated under ICF subdomain code d550.

- The Polarity of the Action = *unable*, meaning the patient cannot feed herself

2. Text whose meaning is too broad is not annotated even if it could reflect the patient’s ability to perform SCDL activities.

Example: Patient lives independently

3. There are instances where SCDL related information is not performed by the patient. In the following example it is not the patient that performs the actions, it is the family, therefore the family cannot be annotated as an Assistance mention.

Example: Patient defers to family members for meal preparation, laundry and shopping

The entire phrase is annotated as SCDL mention.

- type = *subjective*
- subject = *other*

- timeline = *present*

The phrase “defers to family members” is NOT considered an Assistance mention since the family are performing the activity for the patient, not just assisting the patient. However, it is not clear if the patient cannot do the activities or can do the activities but defers, as a choice, to others.

The Action mentions “meal preparation”, “laundry”, and “shopping” are annotated under ICF codes d630, d640, and d620, respectively.

- The polarity of all three Actions = *unclear*

4. Annotating partially met goals: The phrase “partially met goals” means that some goals were met and some were not or that part of a goal was met but not fully. In rehabilitation or therapy notes, annotate partially met goals that relate to SCDL mentions with timeline = *future* as connotes that there are still unmet goals and therapy is on-going and addressing these goals in the future. The exception is in discharge notes or combined admission/discharge notes with a one-time assessment and treatment encounter where no further therapy will occur in the future, annotations of partially met goals will have a timeline = *past*.

Example 1: Identify at least 2 specific coping skills she has learned to manage symptoms in order to promote active engagement in health management in preparation for returning to supported living in the community (goal partially met).

5. SCDL text spans: As a general principle, annotate the shortest span of text as SCDL mentions and exclude reasons for performing or not performing SCDL related activities (e.g., in preparation for...)

Example 1: The patient presents with a NIHFA score of 20/24 indicating modified independence in the six basic areas of self-care especially when it comes to lower body tasks.

Example 2: Participate in at least 2 meal preparation tasks with set-up and minimal prompting in order to engage in an essential daily living activity in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

6. For instances where the text can be somewhat confusing or there is a contradiction, annotate for the meaning that can be discerned.

Example 1: Needs help with her own personal hygiene without assistance

The entire phrase is annotated as a SCDL mention.

- type = *subjective*
- subject = *patient*
- timeline = *present*

The phrase “Needs help” would be the Assistance mention with attributes:

- polarity = *unclear*
- source = *person*

The action mentions “Personal Hygiene” is annotated under ICF code d520

- The polarity of the Action = *unclear*

The phrase “Without assistance” would be the Assistance mention with attributes:

- polarity = *unclear*
- source = *no_source*

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9 REFERENCES

- AOTA. (2020). Occupational therapy practice framework: Domain and process (4th ed.). *American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 74, 7412410010p7412410011 – 7412410010p7412410087. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.2020.74S2001>
- Bickenbach, J., Rubinelli, S., Baffone, C., & Stucki, G. (2023). The human functioning revolution: Implications for health systems and sciences. *Frontiers in Science*, 1(1118512), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsci.2023.1118512>
- Cunningham, H., Maynard, D., & Bontcheva, K. (2011). *Text processing with GATE*. Gateway Press.
- Hasan, S. A., & Farri, O. (2019). Clinical natural language processing with deep learning. In *Data science for health care: Methodologies and applications* (pp. 147-171). Springer.
- National Library of Medicine. (2019). *SNOMED CT* <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/healthit/snomedct/index.html>
- Newman-Griffis, D., Porcino, J., Zirikly, A., Thieu, T., Camacho Maldonado, J., Ho, P. S., Ding, M., Chan, L., & Rasch, E. (2019). Broadening horizons: the case for capturing function and the role of health informatics in its use. *BMC Public Health*, 19(1), 1288. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7630-3>
- World Health Organization. (2001). *International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: ICF*. World Health Organization.

APPENDIX 1: SCDL Codes and Definitions

These Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) codes are the codes published and available on the World Health Organization's (WHO) International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) ICF browser and on the UMLS SNOMED CT cite at the time the guideline was developed. The ICF continues to add codes to the online browser. We recommended users check the [ICF online browser](#) for the most updated classification and codes.

The table below displays ICF and SNOMED CT SCDL codes and definitions. ICF codes are displayed with 3-digit parent codes and 4-digit child codes. **Only the seven Self-Care and four Domestic Life 3-digit codes listed below and bolded were used for annotation.** The 4-digit child codes are displayed and defined for the benefit of the reader to provide greater conceptual clarity to the parent code.

ICF Self-Care Codes and Definitions		
Code	Name	Description
d510	Washing oneself	Washing and drying one's whole body, or body parts, using water and appropriate cleaning and drying materials or methods, such as bathing, showering, washing hands and feet, face and hair, and drying with a towel.
d5100	Washing body parts	Applying water, soap and other substances to body parts, such as hands, face, feet, hair or nails, in order to clean them.
d5101	Washing whole body	Applying water, soap and other substances to the whole body in order to clean oneself, such as taking a bath or shower.
d5102	Drying oneself	Using a towel or other means for drying some part or parts of one's body, or the whole body, such as after washing.
d520	Caring for body parts	Looking after those parts of the body, such as skin, face, teeth, scalp, nails and genitals, that require more than washing and drying.
d5200	Caring for skin	Looking after the texture and hydration of one's skin, such as by removing calluses or corns and using moisturizing lotions or cosmetics.
d5201	Caring for teeth	Looking after dental hygiene, such as by brushing teeth, flossing, and taking care of a dental prosthesis or orthosis.
d5202	Caring for hair	Looking after the hair on the head and face, such as by combing, styling, shaving, or trimming.
d5203	Caring for fingernails	Cleaning, trimming or polishing the nails of the fingers.
d5204	Caring for toenails	Cleaning, trimming or polishing the nails of the toes.
d5205	Caring for nose	Cleaning the nose, looking after nasal hygiene.
d5206	Caring for ears	Cleaning ears and looking after ears hygiene.

d530	Toileting	Planning and carrying out the elimination of human waste (menstruation, urination and defecation), and clean oneself afterwards.
d5300	Regulating urination	Coordinating and managing urination, such as by indicating need, getting into the proper position, choosing and getting to an appropriate place for urination, manipulating clothing before and after urination, and cleaning oneself after urination.
d5301	Regulating defecation	Coordinating and managing defecation such as by indicating need, getting into the proper position, choosing and getting to an appropriate place for defecation, manipulating clothing before and after defecation, and cleaning oneself after defecation.
d5302	Menstrual care	Coordinating, planning and caring for menstruation, such as by anticipating menstruation and using sanitary towels and napkins.
d540	Dressing	Carrying out the coordinated actions and tasks of putting on and taking off clothes and footwear in sequence and in keeping with climatic and social conditions, such as by putting on, adjusting and removing shirts, skirts, blouses, pants, undergarments, saris, kimono, tights, hats, gloves, coats, shoes, boots, sandals and slippers.
d5400	Putting on clothes	Carrying out the coordinated tasks of putting clothes on various parts of the body, such as putting clothes on over the head, over the arms and shoulders, and on the lower and upper halves of the body; putting on gloves and headgear.
d5401	Taking off clothes	Carrying out the coordinated tasks of taking clothes off various parts of the body, such as pulling clothes off and over the head, off the arms and shoulders, and off the lower and upper halves of the body; taking off gloves and headgear.
d5402	Putting on footwear	Carrying out the coordinated tasks of putting on socks, stockings and footwear.
d5403	Taking off footwear	Carrying out the coordinated tasks of taking off socks, stockings and footwear.
d5404	Choosing appropriate clothing	Following implicit or explicit dress codes and conventions of one's society or culture and dressing in keeping with climatic conditions.
d550	Eating	Carrying out the coordinated tasks and actions of eating food that has been served, bringing it to the mouth and consuming it in culturally acceptable ways, cutting or breaking food into pieces, opening containers and packets, using eating implements, having meals, feasting or dining.
d560	Drinking	Taking hold of a drink, bringing it to the mouth, and consuming the drink in culturally acceptable ways, mixing, stirring and

		pouring liquids for drinking, opening bottles and cans, drinking through a straw or drinking running water such as from a tap or a spring; feeding or suckling from the breast.
d570	Looking after one's health	Ensuring physical comfort, health and physical and mental well-being, such as by maintaining a balanced diet, and an appropriate level of physical activity, keeping warm or cool, avoiding harms to health, following safe sex practices, such as using condoms, getting immunizations and regular physical examinations.
d5700	Ensuring one's physical comfort	Caring for oneself by being aware that one needs to ensure, and ensuring, that one's body is in a comfortable position, that one is not feeling too hot, cold or wet, and that one has adequate lighting.
d5701	Managing diet and fitness	Caring for oneself by being aware of the need and by selecting and consuming nutritious foods and maintaining physical fitness.
d5702	Maintaining one's health	Caring for oneself by being aware of the need and doing what is required to look after one's health, both to respond to risks to health and to prevent ill-health, such as by seeking assistance (professional and non-professional); following medical and other health advice; and managing risks to health such as injuries, communicable diseases, drug-taking and sexual transmitted diseases.
ICF Domestic Life Codes and Definitions		
d610	Acquiring a place to live	Buying, renting, furnishing and arranging a room, house, apartment or other dwelling.
d6100	Buying a place to live	Acquiring ownership of a house, apartment or other dwelling.
d6101	Renting a place to live	Acquiring the use of a house, apartment or other dwelling belonging to another in exchange for payment.
d6102	Furnishing a place to live	Equipping and arranging a living space with furniture, fixtures and other fittings and decorating rooms, arranging ones own space, room.
d620	Acquisition of goods and services	Selecting, procuring and transporting all goods and services required for daily living, such as selecting, procuring, transporting and storing food, drink, clothing, cleaning materials, fuel, household items, utensils, cooking ware, play and recreational materials, domestic appliances and tools; procuring utilities and other household services, and picking up and delivering paper mail or packages.
d6200	Shopping	Obtaining, in exchange for money, goods and services required for daily living (including instructing and supervising an

		intermediate to do the shopping), such as selecting food, drink, cleaning materials, household items, play and recreational materials or clothing in a shop or market; comparing quality and price of the items required, negotiating and paying for selected goods or services and transporting goods.
d6201	Gathering daily necessities	Obtaining, without exchange of money, goods and services required for daily living (including instructing and supervising an intermediate to gather daily necessities), such as by harvesting vegetable and fruits, getting water and fuel and picking up and delivering paper mail or packages.
d630	Preparing meals	Planning, organizing, cooking and serving simple and complex meals for oneself and others, such as by making a menu, selecting edible food and drink, getting together ingredients for preparing meals, cooking with heat and preparing cold foods and drinks, and serving the food.
d6301	Preparing simple meals	Planning, organizing, cooking and serving meals with small number of ingredients that require easy methods of preparation and serving, such as making a snack or small meal, and transforming food ingredients by cutting and stirring, boiling and heating food such as rice or potatoes.
d6302	Preparing complex meals	Planning, organizing, cooking and serving meals with large number of ingredients that require complex methods of preparation and serving, such as planning a meal with several dishes, and transforming food ingredients by combined actions of peeling, slicing, mixing, kneading, stirring, presenting and serving food in a manner appropriate to the occasion and culture.
d640	Doing housework	Managing a household by cleaning the house, washing clothes, using household appliances, storing food and disposing of garbage, such as by sweeping, mopping, washing counters, walls and other surfaces; collecting and disposing of household garbage; tidying rooms, closets and drawers; collecting, washing, drying, folding and ironing clothes; cleaning footwear; using brooms, brushes and vacuum cleaners; using washing machines, dryers and irons.
d6400	Washing and drying clothes and garments	Washing and drying clothes and garments
d6401	Cleaning cooking area and utensils	Cleaning up after cooking, such as by washing dishes, pans, pots and cooking utensils, and cleaning tables and floors around cooking and eating area.
d6402	Cleaning living area	Cleaning the living areas of the household, such as by tidying and dusting, sweeping, swabbing, mopping floors, cleaning

		windows and walls, cleaning bathrooms and toilets, cleaning household furnishings.
d6403	Using household appliances	Using all kinds of household appliances, such as washing machines, driers, irons, vacuum cleaners, dishwashers.
d6404	Storing daily necessities	Storing food, drinks, clothes and other household goods required for daily living; preparing food for conservation by canning, salting or refrigerating, keeping food fresh and out of the reach of animals.
d6405	Disposing of garbage	Disposing of household garbage such as by collecting trash and rubbish around the house, preparing garbage for disposal, using garbage disposal appliances; burning garbage.
d650	Caring for household objects	Maintaining and repairing household and other personal objects, including play material, house and contents, clothes, play and recreational materials, vehicles and assistive devices, and caring for plants and animals, such as painting or wallpapering rooms, fixing furniture, repairing plumbing, ensuring the proper working order of vehicles, watering plants, grooming and feeding pets and domestic animals and taking care of entrances, walkways and driveways.
d6500	Making and repairing clothes	Making and repairing clothes, such as by sewing, producing or mending clothes; reattaching buttons and fasteners; ironing clothes, fixing and polishing footwear.
d6501	Maintaining dwelling and furnishings	Repairing and taking care of dwelling, its exterior, interior and contents, such as by painting, repairing fixtures and furniture, and using required tools for repair work.
d6502	Maintaining domestic appliances	Repairing and taking care of all domestic appliances for cooking, cleaning and repairing, such as by oiling and repairing tools and maintaining the washing machine.
d6503	Maintaining vehicles	Repairing and taking care of motorized and non-motorized vehicles for personal use, including bicycles, carts, automobiles and boats.
d6504	Maintaining assistive devices	Repairing and taking care of assistive devices such as prostheses, orthoses and specialized tools and aids for housekeeping and personal care; maintaining and repairing aids for personal mobility such as canes, walkers, wheelchairs and scooters; and maintaining communication and recreational aids.
d6505	Taking care of plants, indoors and outdoors	Taking care of plants inside and outside the house, such as by planting, watering and fertilizing plants; gardening and growing foods for personal use.
d6506	Taking care of animals	Taking care of domestic animals and pets, such as by feeding, cleaning, grooming and exercising pets; watching over the health of animals or pets; planning for the care of animals or pets in one's absence.

d6507	Taking care of walkways and driveways	Taking care of domestic pathways such as walkways and driveways or entrances to houses (covered or uncovered) for example removing snow, leaves, rubble or sand from entrances as well as spreading sand or other material.
d660	Assisting others	Assisting household members and others with their learning, communicating, self-care, movement, within the house or outside; being concerned about the well-being of household members and others.
d6600	Assisting others with self-care	Assisting household members and others in performing self-care, including helping others with eating, bathing and dressing; taking care of children or members of the household who are sick or have difficulties with basic self-care; helping others with their toileting.
d6601	Assisting others in movement	Assisting household members and others in movements and in moving outside the home, such as in the neighborhood or city, to or from school, place of employment or other destination.
d6602	Assisting others in communication	Assisting household members and others with their communication, such as by helping with speaking, writing or readings.
d6603	Assisting others in interpersonal relations	Assisting household members and others with their interpersonal interactions, such as by helping them to initiate, maintain or terminate relationships.
d6604	Assisting others in nutrition	Assisting household members and others with their nutrition, such as by helping them to prepare and eat meals.
d6605	Assisting others in health maintenance	Assisting household members and others with formal and informal health care, such as by ensuring that a child gets regular medical check-ups, or that an elderly relative takes required medication.

SNOMED CT Self-Care Codes and Definitions		
Code	Name	Description
285033005	Ability to manage medication (observable entity)	"Manage medication" includes organizing, obtaining and taking prescribed medications.
709007004	Compliance behavior to therapeutic regimen	"Therapy" includes participating in therapeutic individual or group sessions.

APPENDIX 2: Annotated Note for SCDL

Below is a synthetic occupational therapy evaluation note that has been annotated for Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) information according to the provided legend. Note that any information that resembles PII or PHI does not pertain to any real individual.

Legend:

SCDL mention

Action mention

Assistance mention

Quantification mention

Score definition mention

Instructions/Questions mention

OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY EVALUATION NOTE

Details:

Visit Type During This Encounter: Inpatient

Date Of Evaluation Visit: 05/01/2020

Diagnosis: Schizophrenia

Additional Referrals To RMD Services: Recreation therapy; Vocational rehab

English As Preferred Language For Healthcare: Yes

Subjective:

Patient/Others Comments: Corey Finch is a 23-year old male currently living with his parents. He was pleasant though reserved on approach and agreeable to participate in interview. Affect was blunted but able to smile at times, though eye contact was poor. He answered questions with short replies and latency noted in response to questions. He reported that his main concerns at this time are his "disturbing thoughts."

Objective:

Observations/Interview Data: Corey was seen for occupational therapy evaluation on 5/9/20, OT Cooking Group on 5/6/20, and an AMPS (Assessment of Motor and Process Skills) on 5/12/20. Occupational performance was analyzed via chart review, interview, standardized assessment of ADL/IADL performance, and direct observation of performance in a group setting.

Evaluation yielded the following:

Occupational Profile Performance in Areas of Occupation Activities of Daily Living (ADL):

Casually dressed; adequately groomed. Reported that he takes care of daily grooming without reminders.

Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL):

Community Mobility: Reported that he has a driver's license. Gave conflicting information about whether he has been driving recently. It appears that he currently relies on his family to transport him as needed.

Financial Management: Reported receiving SSDI which is deposited in his account. Reported that he budgets his money appropriately and manages his own account. Stated that his parents supplement his financial support as needed.

Health Management: Reported that his parents assist with setting up and getting him to medical appointments. Stated that **his mother helps set up his medications in a pill box but that he takes them on his own** and may forget a dose approximately once or twice a week. Able to name the names and doses of his antipsychotic medication.

Home Management & Meal Prep: Corey was vague about his responsibilities/participation in household tasks. Reported that **he is responsible for some household tasks such as washing dishes, taking out the trash, and caring for family pets.** Stated that **he does not do his own laundry.** He reported that he helps his mother with **cooking sometimes** and if he wants to make himself food, **he will prepare something simple like oatmeal or a sandwich.**

Shopping: Corey is not responsible for shopping for household supplies. **He reported shopping independently for personal items.**

Education: Corey graduated from HS. He attended a 4-year college full-time for two years and part-time for another year, studying marine biology. He was unable to continue after the onset of symptoms. Reported that he would like to complete his degree.

Work: Corey reported that his last job was "a while back" during summers when he worked as a lifeguard at a local community swimming pool.

Leisure: listening to music, following sports, following current events/watching news programs

Social Participation: It does not appear that Corey has social contact with anyone outside of his immediate family. Reported withdrawing from friends after the onset of his symptoms and does not identify any current friends or social activities. Stated that he gets very anxious in social situations, especially around women who might think "I'm weird."

Client Factors: Corey lost his 10-year-old sister and only sibling when he was 8 years old due to a motor vehicle accident. He reported that he was on the swim team in high school and college before he had to drop out. He has been discouraged by his recent weight gain and he is interested in getting back to swimming. Corey was reluctant to discuss the specific nature of his symptoms but reported that his "intrusive thoughts make it hard to function" and he feels "depressed" about his situation. He reported drowsiness from his medications which causes him difficulty "just getting up and going."

Pain: No pain, 0/10, elicited, observed or reported during this visit

Occupational Performance Skills/Patterns: Corey participated in the Assessment of Motor and Processing Skills (AMPS) on 5/12/20. The AMPS is a standardized evaluation of a person's ability to perform personal and domestic activities of daily living (ADL) tasks. More specifically, when a

person is evaluated using the AMPS, the occupational therapist observes the person perform at least two relevant and chosen ADL tasks. The assessment results are as follows: Performance Skills Motor Skills: (Skills needed to move self and objects)

Effort: Demonstrated average clumsiness and effort during IADL task performance
Areas of difficulty: manipulating objects.

The ADL motor ability measure was 0.8 standard deviations above the normative mean, indicating that 21.1% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL motor ability measure.

Process Skills: (Skills needed to organize and adapt actions to complete task)

Efficiency: Demonstrated mild degree of disorganization and undesirable use of time, space, or objects. The ADL process ability measure was 1.3 standard deviations below the normative mean, indicating that 90.5% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL process ability measure.

Safety: Demonstrated minimal risk for personal injury or environmental damage.

Need for assistance: Demonstrated a minimal degree of need for verbal assistance.

Areas of difficulty: applying knowledge, temporal organization, organizing space and objects, and adapting performance.

Community needs: daily supervision is recommended in the community.

Communication/Interaction Skills: Corey is pleasant and able to make his needs known. However, during the interview and in group setting, Corey appeared preoccupied and had some difficulty attending to interactions. Responded when directly addressed but no spontaneous interactions and there was latency in his responses. Asked for questions to be repeated frequently. However, is well-spoken and able to answer questions appropriately though responses were brief and vague. Able to smile in response to humor.

Habits/Routines/Roles: Corey reported that at home he generally gets up in the late morning (11 AM-12PM) and spends a great deal of time on his computer or engaged in other solitary or passive activities. He used to swim at his local pool 3-4 times a week but stated, "I haven't done that in a while." He appears to have an established ADL/grooming routine though sometimes needs reminders. Reported that he feels he has let his parents down but acknowledges his parents are supportive.

Affected Areas of Occupation: Activities of daily living; Instrumental activities of daily living; Leisure; Education; Vocation; Social participation

Assessment:

Corey's occupational profile is characterized by **modified independence in ADL performance** with **some difficulty managing IADL**, Leisure, Vocation/Education, and Social roles due to experience of symptoms. Though he has been able to live independently in a college setting in the past, he currently relies on the support of his parents. His health condition has limited his present repertoire of occupations and interfered with his ability to achieve age-appropriate roles such as finishing college, working and establishing independent living. His social and community participation are currently very limited. Corey is in the beginning stages of understanding his health condition. He appears motivated to learn more about his health condition and explore options for managing his symptoms. Corey would benefit from occupational therapy services while on the unit to improve engagement in occupations to support participation in desired roles and life situations in home and community.

Strengths: Corey's strengths include willingness to participate in therapy, his past educational and social experiences, his past experience in a variety of leisure activities, and generally cooperative attitude. He identified the following personal strengths: "swimming" and "sciences."

Needs: Corey's needs include further development of coping skills to support engagement in college and work and increasing social/community participation, establishing a health daily routine, and increasing independence in IADLs. Corey identified the following needs: "social skills" and "improve fitness."

Priorities: "get better, lose weight, and finish degree"

NIHFA OT Score (6-24): 23

Need For Other RMD Services: The Patient has been referred to Vocational therapy and Recreational therapy services.

Plan:

Evaluation & Interventions To Be Coordinated With Interdisciplinary Team:

Interventions: Occupational Therapy to be initiated at this time with individual services as specific needs are identified and unit-based programming per tolerance/availability throughout admission. His progress will be reported in treatment planning meeting on a weekly basis.

Goals:

STGs (within 2 weeks): Corey will:

1. attend next OT Cooking Group session and participate in at least 2 meal preparation tasks with set-up and minimal prompting in order to engage in an essential daily living activity in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
2. identify at least 3 topics of interest related to self-management in context of OT self-management group in order to promote active engagement in health management.

LTGs (by discharge): Corey will:

1. identify at least 2 specific coping skills he has learned to manage symptoms in order to promote active engagement in health management in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
2. participate in at least 3 meal preparation tasks in OT Cooking Group with general supervision in order to engage in an essential daily living task in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
3. identify 2 concrete steps he can take to increase social participation in order to strengthen support network upon returning to supported living in the community.
4. participate in Independent Medication Program for 4 days using environmental modifications in order to strengthen self-management skills in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

Patient/Caregiver/Significant Other Actively Participated In Goal Setting: Yes

Response To Care: Patient aware of and agrees to general intervention plan

Education:

Services Provided:

Verbal Education: Received verbal education on role of OT services and objectives of OT group sessions.

Learning Demonstrated As Follows: Patient verbalizes understanding; May benefit from review.

Electronic Signatures:

Mathis, Diedre (OTR/L) (Signed 05/12/2020 15:47)

Authored: Evaluation Note, Subjective, Objective, Assessment, Plan, Education

Last Updated: 05/12/2020 15:47 by Mathis, Deidre (OTR/L)

APPENDIX 3: Abbreviations found in clinical documentation

These abbreviations were taken from the SCDL corpus used for developing annotations and include additional common abbreviations.

IN ACTION MENTIONS:

EOB = Edge of bed

OOB = Out of bed

IN ASSISTANCE MENTIONS:

a.d. = Assist device/ Assistive device

AD = Assistive device

AFO = Ankle foot orthosis

CGA = Contact guard assist

CG = Contact guard

FO = Foot orthosis

FWW = Front wheeled walker

I = Independent

Ind = Independent

KAFO = Knee ankle foot orthosis

Lofstrand crutches = forearm crutches

LRAD = Less restrictive assistive device

MI = Modified independent

Max assist = Maximum assist/Maximal assist

Min A = Minimum assist/Minimal assist

Mod A = Moderate assist

Mod I = Modified Independence

PA = Physical assist

PFRW = platform rolling walker

Pt = Patient

PT = Physical therapist

PT = Physical therapy

QC = quad cane

R/W = Rolling walker/ Rollator walker

Rw = Rolling walker/ Rollator walker

S = Supervised/ Supervision

SBA = Stand by assist

SP cane = Single point cane

SPC = Single point cane

Sup = Supervised/ Supervision

Supv = Supervised/ Supervision

SPV = Supervision

VCs = Verbal cues/ Verbal command

W/C = Wheelchair

OTHERS:

act = activity

B = bilateral or bilaterally

b/i = bilateral

b/l = bilateral

BKA=below knee amputation/amputee

C/C = Chief or current complaint

dec = decline or declining

d/t = due to

HEP = Home Exercise Program

HR = heart rate

LTG = long-term goal

NWB = non-weight bearing

obs = observed

OT = occupational therapist or occupational therapy

PT = physical therapist or physical therapy

STG = short-term goal

Ther ex = therapeutic exercise

TLSO = thoracolumbosacral orthosis

v/s = vital signs

w/ = with

w/o = without

WHO = wrist/hand orthosis